

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 4.3 Support from national governments on delivery of the Implementation Plan

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This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordinated and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

Collective view

This document has been prepared on behalf of the Zero Emissions Platform Advisory Council and the SET-Plan Implementation Plan working group on CCUS (IWG9) Plenary. Views and opinions expressed are the collective views of the Advisory Council and the Plenary, not of individual members or participants

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Contact details:

+32 2 882 50 07

iwg9@zeroemissionsplatform.eu

www.ccus-setplan.eu

www.zeroemissionsplatform.eu

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1 INTRODUCTION

D4.3 Support from national governments on delivery of the Implementation Plan.

The deliverable contains relevant information regarding the work done by national governments to support the deployment of carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon capture and utilisation (CCU), including via the Government Group.

1.1 Belgium

1.1.1 Reduction and removal targets

Belgium's Long-Term Climate Strategy¹ targets a 95% reduction in emissions by 2050 compared to 1990 levels, with the remaining 5% compensated by negative emissions, including in the land use, land-use change, and forestry (LULUCF) based and engineered removals like bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS) and direct air carbon capture and storage (DACCS). However, there are no binding targets on CCS/CCU or carbon dioxide removal (CDR).

1.1.2 Legal framework

Belgium has not adopted any federal climate law. However, the Brussels Region has set a goal of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050, aiming for a 90% reduction in emissions compared to 2005 levels². Similarly, Wallonia's climate law establishes a target for climate neutrality by 2050, calling for emissions reductions ranging from 80% to 95%³. Flanders has not yet passed a Climate Law but suggests achieving carbon neutrality with the help of external negative emissions.

CO₂ storage is allowed in Belgium. Flanders is working on a new decree to facilitate the development of CO₂ capture and transport infrastructure, including non-discriminatory clauses to ensure access to CO₂ infrastructure and to facilitate CO₂ transport between clusters. Wallonia is also developing a legislative and administrative framework to enable the transport and utilisation of CO₂. Belgium has ratified Article 6 of the London Protocol, which pertains to the cross-border transport of CO₂. Additionally, Flanders has developed a regulatory framework for CCS and CCU including CO₂ liquefaction infrastructure and temporary storage.

¹ [National Climate Commission. \(2021\). Belgische Langetermijnstrategie.](#)

² [City of Brussels. \(2022\). City of Brussels Climate Plan.](#)

³ [European Parliament. \(2021\). Climate action in Belgium.](#)

1.1.3 Potential capacity

By 2030, initial projections indicate that Belgian industrial installations, concentrated in the Flemish region, are expected to capture about 5 Mt of CO₂ annually⁴. Beyond 2030, carbon capture capacity is anticipated to extend into both the Flemish and Walloon regions.

Belgium does not have depleted gas and oil deposits in its maritime area. Denmark, Norway, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom are key partners for international cooperation on CO₂ storage.

In Wallonia, the anticipated estimates for 2050 indicate transport and storage opportunities amounting to 6 Mt of CO₂ annually⁵. This aligns with the entire process emissions of the region, including emissions from cement, iron, steel, aluminium, pulp, paper, and refineries.

1.1.4 Research, innovation, and funding

Flanders holds a strategic position within the North-West European industrial cluster and is in proximity to major CO₂ storage sites in the North Sea basin. The region is home to Europe's largest integrated fuel and chemical cluster, resulting in substantial CO₂ emissions concentrated within a relatively small area. The existing or planned pipeline network, clusters, and ports enable efficient CO₂ transport. This positioning makes Flanders an ideal hub for fostering new collaborations and integrating innovative systems for capturing, collecting, or sequestering tens of millions of tonnes of CO₂ or transforming them into valuable products.

Wallonia is implementing several initiatives to foster carbon management. These include establishing a regulatory and administrative framework to facilitate the transport and utilisation of CO₂ in Wallonia, offering support for the development of CO₂ capture and sequestration projects, as well as related research and development. Additionally, efforts are underway to identify the potential for underground CO₂ storage in Wallonia. It is anticipated that Wallonia may export its CO₂ to Norway.

As indicated in the national energy and climate plans (NECP)⁶, the federal government will continue to create the regulatory framework within its competences at national level to enable CCS.

Flanders is providing funding for multiple CCS projects in the region. Targeted co-financing of promising CCUS projects maximises the success rate of EU grants. Through its support mechanisms, Flanders assists companies in their applications to EU funds.

1.1.5 Projects

Go4Zero Project⁷: aims at decarbonising the Holcim's cement plant in Obourg using CCS and will transport the captured CO₂ to underground storage sites.

⁴ [European Commission. \(2023\). Belgium - Draft updated NECP 2021-2030.](#)

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ [Go4Zero.](#)

H2BE Project⁸: operated by Equinor and ENGIE, the project aims at producing hydrogen from natural gas using autothermal reforming technology combined with carbon capture and storage.

Kairos@C Project⁹: Air Liquide and BASF are planning to develop the world's largest cross-border CCS value chain to significantly reduce CO₂ emissions at the industrial cluster in the port of Antwerp, including CO₂ capture, liquefaction, shipping, and storage in the North Sea. The project received a EUR 356 million grant through the Innovation Fund.

Antwerp@C CO₂ Export Hub Project¹⁰: Air Liquide, Fluxys, and the Port of Antwerp-Bruges aim to develop a world-scale open-access modular infrastructure for the transport, liquefaction, and export of CO₂ captured by industries in the Antwerp port area. It received EUR 144.6 million of EU funding for CO₂ capture infrastructure. The hub will have an initial export capacity of 2.5 Mtpa, with the ambition to reach up to 10 Mtpa by 2030.

Steelanol CCU Project¹¹: ArcelorMittal is developing a CCU project at its steel plant in Ghent, using biocatalysts to transform carbon-rich waste gases from the steelmaking process and from waste biomass into advanced ethanol. At full capacity the Steelanol plant will produce 80 million litres of advanced ethanol and reduce annual carbon emissions from the Ghent plant by 125,000 tonnes. The project received EUR 10.2 million of EU funding from the Horizon Europe programme.

Anthemis Project¹²: Heidelberg Materials intends to equip the Antoing cement plant with an innovative hybrid carbon capture unit. Once operational, it will capture around 800,000 tonnes of CO₂ from the cement production process annually.

Columbus Project¹³: ENGIE, Carmeuse, and John Cockerill are developing an innovative CCU project in Wallonia at ENGIE's Amercoeur power plant to create e-methane by capturing carbon and reacting it with green hydrogen.

⁸ [Engie. \(2023\). ENGIE & Equinor launch the H2BE project to kick-start low-carbon hydrogen market in Belgium.](#)

⁹ [Air Liquide. \(2021\). Air Liquide and BASF welcome support from European Innovation Fund for joint CCS project.](#)

¹⁰ [Air Liquide. \(2022\). Air Liquide, Fluxys Belgium and Port of Antwerp-Bruges awarded EU funding for building the Antwerp@C CO₂ Export Hub.](#)

¹¹ [ArcelorMittal. \(n.d.\). ArcelorMittal inaugurates flagship carbon capture and utilisation project at its steel plant in Ghent, Belgium.](#)

¹² [Heidelberg Materials. \(2023\). Heidelberg Materials to build one-of-a-kind hybrid carbon capture unit at its Belgian Antoing cement plant.](#)

¹³ [Engie. \(n.d.\). Columbus.](#)

1.1.6 Bilateral agreements

Belgium and Denmark: MoU on the cross-border transportation of CO₂ between the two countries with the purpose of permanent geological storage¹⁴.

Belgium and Germany: agreement to cooperate on hydrogen, carbon capture, electrification and LNG projects as part of efforts to increase energy independence and decarbonise¹⁵.

Belgium and the Netherlands: MoU on the cross-border transportation of CO₂ between the two countries with the purpose of permanent geological storage¹⁶.

Belgium and Norway: negotiations for a bilateral agreement on the cross-border transport and storage of CO₂ on the Norwegian Continental Shelf, under the London Protocol¹⁷.

1.2 Czechia

1.2.1 Reduction and removal targets

Czechia has committed to reaching climate neutrality by 2050. Following the revision of the EU Climate Law, it must reach a 26% emissions reductions target by 2030 compared to 2005 levels in sectors not covered by the EU Emission Trading System (EU ETS).

The Czech draft updated version of its NECP¹⁸ states that there will be 6.3 MtCO₂ of residual emissions by 2050, and the LULUCF sector is currently a net emitter, with 15 MtCO₂e emissions in 2021. This underscores the significant challenges Czechia faces in reducing the sector's emissions to zero. It identifies CCS and CCU as one of eight strategic priorities. It specifies that these technologies should be employed only for hard-to-abate emissions, projected to total 18 MtCO₂ by 2050. The plan also mentions BECCS and DACCS as potential technologies to address residual emissions, although their roles in the country's climate strategy are not clearly defined.

¹⁴ [Flanders Chancellery & Foreign Office. \(2022\). Memorandum of understanding between the Minister for Environment of the Flemish Region and the Federal Minister for the North Sea of Belgium and the Minister for Climate, Energy, and Utilities of Denmark on cross border transportation of CO₂ with the purpose of permanent geological storage.](#)

¹⁵ [Belgian-German Joint Declaration on Bilateral Cooperation on the Transition to Sustainable Carbon Neutral Economies.](#)

¹⁶ [Memorandum of understanding between the Minister for Environment of the Flemish Region and the Federal Minister for the North Sea of Belgium and the Minister for Energy and Climate of the Walloon Region and the Minister of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy of the Netherlands on cross border transportation of CO₂ with the purpose of permanent geological storage.](#)

¹⁷ [Regjeringen.no. \(2023\). Belgium and Norway will work closer on cross-border transport and storage of CO₂.](#)

¹⁸ [European Commission. \(2023\). Update of the Czech National Plan of the Republics in the field of energy and climate.](#)

Furthermore, the draft NECP highlights that biogas production is well-suited for CCS, potentially leading to negative emissions and thus qualifying as CDR. According to government models, CCS and CCU are not anticipated to be implemented before 2035.

The Czech long-term climate strategy¹⁹ has not been updated since 2017 and is currently under revision, with an unknown timeframe for completion. The State Environmental Policy of the Czech Republic 2030 with outlook to 2050²⁰, outlines the main environmental policy actions for the country. It is structured around three main pillars: (1) environment and health; (2) transition to climate neutrality and the circular economy; and (3) nature and landscape. The State Energy Policy²¹, also not updated since 2017, mentions geological CO₂ storage as a sub-aim for a more effective utilisation of fossil energy sources. However, it only briefly mentions CCS and does not elaborate on its potential role within the policy.

1.2.2 Legal framework

The Act on the Storage of Carbon Dioxide into Natural Rock Structures and Amending Certain Acts²² is the cornerstone of Czechia's CO₂ storage legal framework, implementing the EU CCS Directive into national law. Until January 1, 2020, this act prohibited commercial geological CO₂ storage. Although this restriction has been lifted, the act still limits commercial CO₂ storage to 1MtCO₂ per year for each storage site. Additionally, it poses challenges for cross-border CO₂ storage, as such storage is prohibited where there is a risk of CO₂ leakage²³.

Czechia is not a party to either the London Convention or the London Protocol. Consequently, to export CO₂ for under-seabed geological storage, the country would need to adopt the standards set by the Protocol and establish bilateral agreements with the receiving countries.

1.2.3 Potential capacity

A 2022 study on Czech decarbonisation pathways by the Charles University Environment Centre estimates that CCS could capture up to 20 MtCO₂ per year by 2050²⁴.

¹⁹ [Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic. \(2017\). Climate protection policy of the Czech Republic executive summary.](#)

²⁰ [Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic. \(2021\). State Environmental Policy of the Czech Republic 2030 with outlook to 2050.](#)

²¹ [Ministry of Industry and Trade. \(2014\). State energy policy of the Czech Republic.](#)

²² [Zákony pro lidi. \(2012\). Zákon č. 85/2012 Sb.](#)

²³ [Bartovic et al. \(n.d.\) Building momentum for the long-term CCS deployment in the CEE region: assessment of current state, past experiences and potential for CCS deployment in the CEE region.](#)

²⁴ [Univerzita Karlova. \(2022\). Vývoj elektro-energetiky a teplárenství v ČR: technologický mix, spotřeba paliv a produkce emisí 2020-2050.](#)

1.2.4 Research, innovation, and funding

The National R&D&I Policy of Czechia 2016-2020²⁵ set broad guidelines for the country's overall research, development, and innovation strategy. The Research Development and Innovation Strategy of the Ministry of Agriculture 2023-2032²⁶ identifies key strategic R&D and innovation areas, including the bioeconomy (utilising biological waste and bio-materials in construction), smart agriculture and forestry, and carbon farming practices. Biodiversity, soils, and forests are crucial focal points throughout the strategy.

The National Priorities for Oriented Research²⁷, released in 2012 and valid until 2030, do not explicitly mention CDR or CCS, however, some workstreams are indirectly relevant to carbon removal. For instance, one biodiversity workstream focuses on increasing the long-term efficiency of the LULUCF sector and promoting environmentally friendly technologies that reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

To support the implementation of these strategies, the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic runs several funding programs combining national and EU funding²⁸. Among these are ERA-NET programme funds for projects related to climate and biodiversity restoration²⁹. The upcoming THÉTA II programme aims to transform and modernise the energy sector and may include relevant calls for CO₂ storage³⁰. Additionally, a national consortium of Czech universities is conducting the Bio-CCS project, which explores bioenergy with carbon capture and storage.

Several projects receive grants from the KAPPA programme for applied research, experimental development, and innovation³¹. The programme is funded by the EEA and Norway and is scheduled to run from 2020 to 2024, spanning five years. One or two calls for proposals were anticipated during this period. The first open call was launched on November 20, 2019. Projects under this programme must have a minimum duration of 24 months and can be implemented for up to five years. All projects must be completed by April 30, 2024, at the latest.

The “building momentum for the long-term CCS deployment in the CEE region” project³² is funded by Iceland, Liechtenstein, and Norway through the EEA and Norway Grants Fund for Regional Cooperation.

²⁵ [Government of the Czech Republic. \(2016\). National Research, Development and Innovation Policy of the Czech Republic 2016–2020.](#)

²⁶ [Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic. \(2022\). Research, Development and Innovation Strategy of the Ministry of Agriculture for 2023 – 2032.](#)

²⁷ [Czechresearch.com. \(2012\). National priorities of oriented research, experimental development and innovations.](#)

²⁸ [TACR. \(n.d.\). Programmes & calls.](#)

²⁹ [TACR. \(n.d.\). ERA-NET Cofunds & European Partnerships.](#)

³⁰ [Weber & Čápková. \(2023\). Programme to support applied research and innovation in the energy sector.](#)

³¹ [TACR. \(n.d.\). KAPPA programme.](#)

³² [Bartovic et al. \(n.d.\) Building momentum for the long-term CCS deployment in the CEE region: assessment of current state, past experiences and potential for CCS deployment in the CEE region.](#)

1.2.5 Projects

A relatively recent research project includes “ENabling Onshore CO2 Storage in Europe” in 2020³³. More recent projects include the METAMORPH project that aims to develop a “*new solution for simultaneous carbon capture and photocatalysis*”³⁴. As a part of the Norway Grants project, Czech company InoCure cooperated with the University of Chemistry and Technology in Prague as well as Jan Evangelista Purkyně University in Ústí nad Labem. The project is supported by SINTEF. The final product is a membrane-based system that should be tested in simulated industrial settings. The project is due to end in 2024.

The KAPPA programme, primarily financed by grants from the EEA and Norway, has a secondary focus on CCS, with about EUR 5 million available³⁵. Several CCS projects in Czechia have received grants from this programme, including REPP-CO2³⁶, a research pilot project on CO2 geological storage, and the CO2-SPICER project, another CO2 storage pilot in a carbonate reservoir³⁷. This project will end in April 2024. The Czech Geological Survey leads this project together with MND, a Czech oil and gas company, the Technical University of Ostrava, the Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, and NORCE, the Norwegian Research Centre. The objective is to lay the ground for a first CO2 storage pilot project in Czechia. The project could potentially lead to CO2 injection eventually and should increase the technological readiness level of CO2 storage in Czechia³⁸.

1.2.6 Bilateral agreements

No bilateral agreements have been identified.

1.3 Denmark

1.3.1 Reduction and removal targets

Denmark aims to become climate neutral by 2045, and to decrease GHG emissions by 70% in 20230, and by 110% in 2050 compared to 1990 levels, relying on removals in the LULUCF sector to counterbalance residual emissions³⁹.

³³ [ENabling Onshore CO2 Storage in Europe.](#)

³⁴ [METAMORPH - Advanced hybrid organic-inorganic nanofibers for CO2 capture and photocatalysis.](#)

³⁵ [TACR. \(n.d.\). KAPPA programme.](#)

³⁶ [Czech Geological Survey. \(n.d.\). REPP-CO2.](#)

³⁷ [Norway Grants. \(n.d.\) CO2Spicer.](#)

³⁸ [Bartovic et al. \(n.d.\) Building momentum for the long-term CCS deployment in the CEE region: assessment of current state, past experiences and potential for CCS deployment in the CEE region.](#)

³⁹ [Statsministeriet. \(2022\). Regeringsgrundlag 2022.](#)

1.3.2 Legal framework

CO₂ storage is permitted in Denmark, which aims to become a carbon storage hub, offering part of its substantial geological CO₂ storage capacity to other European countries. A TotalEnergies consortium has received two exploration licenses, with an expected storage capacity of 2-3 Mtpa in 2029-2030, increasing to 10-15 Mtpa by 2030-2032. Similarly, an INEOS consortium has been granted both a pilot storage permit and a full-scale exploration permit to develop the first cross-border offshore CCS initiative, aiming for a storage capacity of up to 1.5 Mtpa in 2025 and up to 8 Mtpa by 2030. Additionally, the Danish Energy Agency has opened applications for permits to explore CO₂ storage possibilities in five selected onshore areas.

The draft updated NECP⁴⁰ includes the deployment of various modes of transport for captured CO₂, such as pipelines, maritime transport, and trucks to connect emitters with storage sites. Discussions regarding the establishment of a national CO₂ transport network are ongoing. Denmark has also ratified Article 6 of the London Protocol, allowing for the transborder transport of CO₂.

In terms of carbon removal, the Danish Energy Agency's scenarios for 2050⁴¹ assess the potential contributions of CDR methods, including BECCS, DACCS, biochar, and forest sinks. These projections suggest that these methods could collectively generate negative emissions of up to 13 Mt of CO₂ equivalent by 2050. Denmark has signed the Aalborg Declaration, identifying CCS and CCU as crucial technologies for the green transition and achieving net-zero emissions by 2050. Furthermore, the Danish parliament has developed a CCS strategy⁴², emphasising the country's commitment to using CCS and CCS-based CDR methods to meet its climate goals.

1.3.3 Potential capacity

The National Geological Studies for Denmark and Greenland (GEUS) has identified an estimated geological CO₂ storage capacity of eight provisionally identified structures, amounting to 12,000 Mt in saline aquifers and at least 10,000 Mt or more in other identified structures⁴³. The GEUS is currently exploring and mapping 8 potential land and coastal storage sites.

The draft updated NECP indicates that 8.9 to 17.9 Mt CO₂ will be captured annually by 2025, with CO₂ captured from biogenic sources amounting to 6.3-12.5 Mt annually. It is mentioned that estimates made for 2030 and 2040 are uncertain:

- starting 2030, the estimated capture volume is 6.9 to 13.7 Mt of CO₂ annually, out of which CO₂ captured from biogenic sources amounts to 5.1-10.1 Mt annually.

⁴⁰ [European Commission. \(2023\). Denmark - Draft Updated NECP 2021-2030.](#)

⁴¹ [Energistyrelsen. \(2022\). Resultater for KP22-scenarier.](#)

⁴² [Klima-, Energi- og Forsyningsministeriet. \(2021\). En køreplan for fangst, transport og lagring af CO₂: anden del af en samlet CCS-strategi.](#)

⁴³ [De Nationale Geologiske Undersøgelser for Danmark og Grønland. \(n.d.\). Fangst og lagring af CO₂ \(CCS\).](#)

- starting 2040, the plan puts forward an estimation of 5.4 to 10.8 Mt of CO₂ to be captured annually, with 3.9-7.7 Mtpa of CO₂ being captured annually from biogenic sources.

The draft updated NECP also mentions two onshore projects with an annual capacity of more than 10 Mt by 2030.

1.3.4 Research, innovation, and funding

The government plans to fund novel CDR methods, such as pyrolysis for biochar production, and further support for BECCS projects and applications⁴⁴.

Denmark participates in the North Sea Basin Task Force, a collaborative initiative working towards the development of common principles for the transportation, injection, and permanent storage of CO₂.

The Danish Energy Agency has awarded the first onshore carbon storage exploration licenses in Denmark to Wintershall Dea, INEOS E&P, CarbonCuts, Equinor, and Ørsted in three locations: Gassum, Rødby, and Havnsø⁴⁵. This initiative is aimed at assessing the potential for safe and responsible carbon storage to aid in meeting climate targets. The companies will conduct detailed investigations to confirm suitability before applying for storage licenses, positioning Denmark as a key player in carbon storage for Europe.

The draft updated NECP mentions that more than DKK 35 billion has been allocated to implementing CCS/CCU as a climate tool⁴⁶.

Denmark's Energy Technology Development and Demonstration Programme (EUDP)⁴⁷ provides funding for the demonstration of innovative green technologies, including those focused on geological CO₂ storage and direct air capture. So far, the EUDP has supported more than 1,200 innovative projects with about DKK 6.2 billion.

The Finance Act of 2022 established a subsidy pool⁴⁸ for facilities generating negative emissions aiming to annually remove up to 0.5 Mt of CO₂ from the atmosphere by 2025. In addition, a CCS/CCU subsidy pool⁴⁹ provides subsidy opportunities to CCS/CCU installations capturing CO₂ at energy-intensive industrial facilities, waste plants, and heat and power plants. It is expected to generate an annual total of 0.4 Mt CO₂ emission reductions by 2025.

⁴⁴ [Klima-, Energi- og Forsyningsministeriet. \(2022\). Appendiks 2 - Virkemiddelkatalog til Klimaprogramme2022.](#)

⁴⁵ [Danish Energy Agency. \(2024\). First licenses in Danish history to explore onshore CO₂ storage potentials awarded.](#)

⁴⁶ [European Commission. \(2023\). Denmark - Draft Updated NECP 2021-2030.](#)

⁴⁷ [Det Energiteknologiske Udviklings- og Demonstrationsprogram. \(n.d.\). About the EUDP.](#)

⁴⁸ [Klima-, Energi- og Forsyningsministeriet. \(n.d.\). Den samlede strategiske indsats for udbredelse af fangst og lagring af CO₂.](#)

⁴⁹ [Klima-, Energi- og Forsyningsministeriet. \(n.d.\). Tilskudspuljer til fangst og lagring af CO₂.](#)

The NECCS (Negative Emissions Carbon Capture and Storage) fund is aimed at achieving negative CO₂ emissions by 2025/26 by providing financial support for projects that capture and store carbon dioxide⁵⁰. The fund is structured to ensure that the aid provided does not result in overcompensation for beneficiaries. A key component of the NECCS fund is the recent inclusion of a "clawback mechanism" mandated by the European Commission. This mechanism is designed to reclaim funds if biogenic CO₂ emissions are later integrated into the EU ETS, ensuring that the support remains fair and aligned with market conditions.

BECCS is expected to become eligible for further funding under the CCS fund from a national green tax reform.

1.3.5 Projects

Ørsted Kalundborg Hub Project⁵¹: Ørsted will establish carbon capture at its wood chip-fired Asnæs Power Station in Kalundborg in western Zealand and at the Avedøre Power Station's straw-fired boiler in the Greater Copenhagen area. Ørsted will capture 430,000 tonnes of biogenic CO₂ per year.

Ruby Project⁵²: aims to establish an onshore CO₂ storage facility at the Rødby coastline. The first storage for CO₂ is expected in 2027 (up to 5 to 10 Mtpa of CO₂).

CO2RYLUS Project⁵³: first onshore CO₂ storage facility in Stenlille, with a minimum storage capacity of 10 Mt of CO₂ per year.

C4 - Carbon Capture Cluster Copenhagen Project⁵⁴: the C4 cluster aims to deploy CCS facilities to capture and store CO₂ in the Copenhagen metropolitan area.

Norne Carbon Storage Hub Project⁵⁵: the Norne hub consists of CO₂ reception facilities at Danish ports and pipelines dedicated to transporting and storing both domestic and international captured CO₂ emissions. This is done through utilisation of two of Denmark's existing natural underground storage structures. Storage capacity up to 20 Mt of CO₂ per year.

Aalborg Portland Project⁵⁶: the objective of this project is to investigate the potential of the carbon capture and storage technology to reduce CO₂ industrial emissions and to allow local communities to share the benefits. A pilot carbon and capture unit has been developed at the Aalborg Portland cement plant. If successful, the project could be scaled up with the potential to capture 400,000 tons of CO₂ per year by 2030.

⁵⁰ [Danish Energy Agency. \(n.d.\). CCS tenders and other funding for CCS development.](#)

⁵¹ [Ørsted. \(n.d.\). Carbon capture and storage.](#)

⁵² [CarbonCuts. \(n.d.\). The Ruby Project.](#)

⁵³ [Gas Storage Denmark. \(n.d.\). CO2RYLUS - CO2 storage in Stenlille.](#)

⁵⁴ [C4 – Carbon Capture Cluster Copenhagen.](#)

⁵⁵ [Norne Carbon Storage Hub. \(n.d.\). Carbon capture and storage.](#)

⁵⁶ [Aalborg Portland Holding. \(n.d.\). Roadmap to 2030.](#)

Greensand Project⁵⁷: aims to establish a value chain for transport and geological CO₂ storage offshore in the Danish North Sea by 2025/2026. Storage capacity potentially could reach up to 8 Mt of CO₂ per year.

Bifrost Project⁵⁸: focuses on enabling permanent geological storage of CO₂ in the Danish North Sea. Potential capacity of 3 Mt of CO₂ per year. The project has been awarded the European project of common European interest (PCI) status.

CHOCO2LATE Project⁵⁹: aims to develop and demonstrate a full process chain from direct air captured CO₂, and turning the CO₂ captured it into fuel.

Carbon Capture Lab⁶⁰: The Danish Technological Institute has opened Denmark's first flexible testing facility for carbon capture, specifically targeting CO₂ capture technologies from biomass burning. The modular facility can generate between 100-2000 cubic meters of flue gas per hour with 8-12% CO₂ content. It serves as an open platform for emitters and technology developers to test and scale up innovative CCS/CCU technologies.

1.3.6 Bilateral agreements

Denmark and Belgium: MoU on the cross-border transportation of CO₂ between the two countries with the purpose of permanent geological storage⁶¹.

Denmark and Germany: Joint declaration of intent to strengthen cooperation in the field of CCS/CCU⁶².

Denmark and the Netherland: MoU to strengthen cooperation in the field of CCS/CCU⁶³.

⁵⁷ [Greensand. \(n.d.\). Hvad er Project Greensand?](#)

⁵⁸ [Bifrost. \(n.d.\). CCS: Bridging the transition to the energy of the future.](#)

⁵⁹ [Det Energiteknologiske Udviklings- og Demonstrationsprogram. \(n.d.\). CHOCO2LATE.](#)

⁶⁰ [Danish Technological Institute. \(2023\). Danish Technological Institute opens Denmark's first flexible testing facility for carbon capture.](#)

⁶¹ [Klima-, Energi- og Forsyningsministeriet. \(2022\). Memorandum of understanding between the Minister for Environment of the Flemish Region and the Federal Minister for the North Sea of Belgium and the Minister for Climate, Energy, and Utilities of Denmark on cross border transportation of CO₂ with the purpose of permanent geological storage.](#)

⁶² [Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz. \(2023\). Joint declaration of intent between the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action of the Federal Republic of Germany and the Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities of Denmark on the cooperation on carbon capture utilisation and storage \(CCUS\).](#)

⁶³ [Memorandum of understanding \(MoU\) between the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy of the Netherlands and the Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities of Denmark on cooperation on carbon capture utilisation and storage \(CCUS\).](#)

Denmark and Norway: MoU to strengthen cooperation in the field of the energy transition in the North Sea, with a special emphasis on CCS/CCU, offshore wind, related offshore grid infrastructure and hydrogen⁶⁴.

Denmark and the UK: MoU to cooperate on a path to net zero and long-term energy security (field of cooperation includes CCS/CCU)⁶⁵.

1.4 France

1.4.1 Reduction and removal targets

In 2020, France adopted the National Low Carbon Strategy⁶⁶, setting the goal of achieving net zero emissions by 2050. The Strategy specifically states that achieving carbon neutrality will require compensating emissions with carbon sinks (forests and farmland), products and materials from the bioeconomy based on plant matter, and industrial processes, including CCS/CCU.

1.4.2 Legal framework

CO₂ storage is permitted in France, with plans to deploy studies evaluating geological storage capacity set for 2024. The country is currently consulting on transportation methods for CO₂, including pipelines, trains, and ships. Additionally, France is in the process of ratifying the amendment of Article 6 of the London Protocol, which pertains to the cross-border transport of CO₂.

France is currently developing a national strategy for CCS/CCU. The French government published its draft strategy⁶⁷ on CCS and CCU in June 2023 and collected feedback from stakeholders through a public consultation in September 2023⁶⁸. The publication of the final strategy is expected in the summer of 2024. The draft strategy includes the following elements:

- A CCS and CCU deployment schedule, with a timetable and volumes of captured CO₂, based on a prioritisation of industrial areas. The strategy highlights the ports of Dunkirk, Le Havre, and Fos-sur-Mer as priority areas.
- A Carbon Contracts for Difference (CCfD) support scheme for CCS projects.
- A legal framework for CO₂ transport infrastructure, covering risk-sharing arrangements (e.g., State guarantee) between the French state, the operators of CO₂ transport infrastructure and their industrial users.

⁶⁴ [Memorandum of understanding between the Ministry of Petroleum and Energy of Norway and the Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities of Denmark on energy cooperation in the North Sea.](#)

⁶⁵ [Department for Energy Security and Net Zero. \(2023\). Cooperation in the energy transition: UK - Denmark memorandum of understanding.](#)

⁶⁶ [Ministry for the Ecological and Solidary Transition. \(2020\). National low carbon strategy: the ecological and inclusive transition towards carbon neutrality.](#)

⁶⁷ [Gouvernement. \(2023\). Stratégie CCUS: capture, stockage, et utilisation du carbone.](#)

⁶⁸ [République Française. \(2023\). Lancement d'une consultation sur la stratégie ccus.](#)

- Diversification of CO₂ storage possibilities with a call for tenders for geological exploration campaigns before the end of 2023 and CO₂ injection tests at pilot sites, with the first tests scheduled for 2024/2025. The ambition amounts to 4 to 8 Mt of CO₂ permanent storage in France by 2030. The French government will also launch information campaigns aimed at facilitating local acceptance.
- The possibility of CCU, to decarbonise the aviation and maritime sectors.

In terms of carbon removal, France adopted the Label Bas-Carbon in 2018. This label provides an official framework to certify emissions reductions and removals at the national level. Furthermore, France has signed the Aalborg Declaration, recognising CCS/CCU as essential technologies to support the green transition and achieve net-zero emissions by 2050.

1.4.3 Potential capacity

The Strategy⁶⁹ anticipates that by 2050 about 10 Mt of negative CO₂ emissions will be generated via BECCS annually, while per year, forests are expected to store about 35 Mt CO₂, wood products 20 Mt CO₂, and other land 10 Mt CO₂.

In the industrial sector, the latest draft of the updated NECP programme indicates that the volumes of CO₂ captured could range from 4 to 8.5 Mt per year by 2030 and between 15 and 20 Mt per year by 2050⁷⁰. The use of CCS in the industrial sector is planned as early as 2027.

Apart from process emissions, France looks at applications for CCS in the production of hydrogen and heat. The NECP programme refers to the possibility to produce bioenergy with carbon capture, with estimates of 1 Mt of CO₂ per year that could be captured in 2040.

France published a call for interest for CCS at different sites to help decarbonise hard-to-abate sectors⁷¹. This call aims to identify CCS actors in France to accelerate the deployment of storage capacity in France. Entities are asked to detail their capacities in terms of CO₂ capture, CO₂ liquefaction, CO₂ transport, CO₂ storage, and CO₂ injection monitoring. Following this first call, a second call could be launched to subsidise CO₂ storage mapping.

1.4.4 Research, innovation, and funding

In 2024, France will launch a new support scheme through Carbon Contracts for Difference (CCfD) to support investments in the deep decarbonisation of industry, in the form of CCUS and other intensive disruptive capital technologies.

⁶⁹ Ibid.

⁷⁰ [Gouvernement. \(2023\). Stratégie CCUS: capture, stockage, et utilisation du carbone.](#)

⁷¹ [Le Ministère de l'Économie et des Finances et de la Souveraineté Industrielle et Numérique. \(2024\). Appel à manifestation d'intérêt - Capture et stockage de carbone.](#)

France does not yet have a geological sequestration capacity for CO₂. Studies to assess these capabilities will be launched in 2024.

France's 2030 investment plan to decarbonise industry⁷² includes:

- An overall budget of EUR 5.6 billion for the development of CCS/CCU technologies.
- EUR 25 to 30 million to support the carrying out of studies or works aimed at improving knowledge of the capacity of the French subsoil in terms of storing CO₂ (seismic campaigns or injectivity tests).

1.4.5 Projects

3D Project (DMX Demonstration in Dunkirk)⁷³: aims to demonstrate an innovative process for capturing CO₂ from industrial activities. The project will realise a comprehensive study dedicated to the development of the future European cluster in Dunkirk for capture and storage in the North Sea. 3D is part of the Horizon 2020 programme and receives EUR 14.8 million in EU subsidies.

GOCO2 Project (Grand-Ouest CO2)⁷⁴: aims to develop an investment programme to capture CO₂ on industrial sites and transport it by pipeline to the Montoir-de-Bretagne terminal for permanent geological storage. The estimated capacity is 2.6 Mt per year by 2030.

CO₂-DISSOLVED Project⁷⁵: aims at storing industrial CO₂ emissions in close saline aquifers while producing geothermal energy for local use.

PilotSTRATEGY Project⁷⁶: funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, the project was officially launched in May 2021. It aims to improve knowledge of the ability of deep saline aquifers to store CO₂ in five industrial regions in southern and eastern Europe. It will also propose the construction of CO₂ storage pilots in three regions of southern Europe, including the Paris Basin.

The 2024 edition of the ICM Forum (previously CCUS Forum) will be jointly organised in Pau (France) by the European Commission and the French government in October 2024⁷⁷.

France is represented in the Union list of projects of common interest and projects of mutual interest⁷⁸, including via:

⁷² [Gouvernement. \(2022\). France 2030: le Premier ministre annonce le déploiement d'actions pour accélérer la décarbonation de l'industrie française.](#)

⁷³ [DMX demonstration Dunkirk.](#)

⁷⁴ [Elengy. \(2023\). GOCO2, Grand-Ouest CO2.](#)

⁷⁵ [CO₂-Dissolved.](#)

⁷⁶ [BRGM. \(2021\). PilotSTRATEGY: CO₂ geological pilots in strategic territories.](#)

⁷⁷ [CCUS Forum and Working Groups - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

⁷⁸ [Official Journal of the European Union. \(2023\). Commission Delegated Regulation \(EU\) 2024/1041 of 28 November 2023 amending Regulation \(EU\) 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the Union list of projects of common interest and projects of mutual interest.](#)

Northern Lights⁷⁹: cross-border connection project between several European capture initiatives, among others Belgium, Germany, Ireland, France, and Sweden.

Callisto⁸⁰: hubs in the Mediterranean storing CO₂ emissions from France and Italy.

Nautilus CCS⁸¹: emissions from Le Havre, Dunkirk, Duisburg, and Rogaland areas to be captured and transported by ship to various sinks in the North Sea.

PYCASSO Project⁸²: programme launched in 2021 to study how CO₂ storage could be developed in south-west France and northern Spain in depleted gas fields and aims at offering onshore storage capacity of 1Mtpa CO₂ in 2030, and further extended to 5 Mtpa in 2035.

1.4.6 Bilateral agreements

France and the Netherlands: signed a Pact for Innovation and Sustainable Growth, including CCS/CCU technologies. The statement highlights that for both countries *“companies are involved in various transport and CO₂ sequestration and reuse projects, aimed at facilitating the large-scale decarbonisation of our two countries' industrial clusters (steel, chemicals, cement, refining and waste incineration, including in the Netherlands”*⁸³.

France and Norway: signed a Letter of Intent to promote mutually beneficial cooperation on the development and deployment of CCS. This partnership includes *“a structured dialogue on CCS to facilitate matchmaking between French and Norwegian businesses in this emerging market”*⁸⁴.

France and Denmark: signed a bilateral agreement under the London Convention and a Letter of Intent to create a political cooperation agreement in March 2024⁸⁵. The bilateral agreement aims to legally allow the transport and storage of CO₂ between the two countries.

⁷⁹ [Northern Lights. \(2022\). Northern Lights designated a Project of Common Interest by the European Union.](#)

⁸⁰ [Snam. \(2023\). Snam: South2 Corridor and Callisto Mediterranean CO₂ Network enter the 6th List of EU Projects of Common Interest \(PCI\).](#)

⁸¹ [Zero Emissions Platform. \(2022\). Process for the 1st Union list of Projects of Common Interest \(PCIs\) and Projects of Mutual Interest \(PMIs\) under the revised TEN-E Regulation.](#)

⁸² [Blaizot et al. \(2022\). The PYCASSO territories Project: a Large Onshore CCUS Hub for Southern Europe.](#)

⁸³ [Le Ministère de l'Économie et des Finances et de la Souveraineté Industrielle et Numérique. \(2023\). France and the Netherlands sign a pact for innovation and sustainable growth.](#)

⁸⁴ [Regjeringen.no. \(2024\). France and Norway sign a strategic partnership on green industrial transformation.](#)

⁸⁵ [Klima-, Energi- og Forsyningsministeriet. \(2024\). Letter of Intent \(LoI\) between the Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities of Denmark and the Ministry of the Economy, Finance and Industrial and Digital Sovereignty of the French Republic on cooperation on carbon capture and storage \(CCS\).](#)

On January 9, 2024, CGG (French) and C-Questra (Dutch) signed a commercial cooperation agreement on CCS/CCU⁸⁶.

During the 2023 edition of the CCUS Forum, France signed the Aalborg Declaration, which states that CCS and CCU are essential technologies that are needed to reach net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050.

1.5 Germany

1.5.1 Reduction and removal targets

Germany aims to achieve carbon neutrality by 2045. Additionally, the Federal Climate Change Act specifies that CO₂ emissions must be reduced by at least 65% by 2030 and by at least 88% by 2040, relative to the emission levels of 1990.

By 2030, the LULUCF sector aims to improve its emissions balance by a minimum of minus 25 Mt of CO₂. This net carbon sink capacity is slated to increase further to at least minus 35 Mt by 2040 and at least minus 40 Mt by 2045.

No binding target on CCS/CCU and CDR (beyond LULUCF related removals).

1.5.2 Legal framework

On 29 May 2024, the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action adopted the German carbon management strategy⁸⁷. The deployment of CCS and CCU must align with the GHG reduction goals of the German Climate Protection Act (KSG) and the aim to achieve climate neutrality by 2045. The Federal Government supports an ambitious implementation of the European Methane Regulation, which includes considering future pricing of upstream emissions from fossil fuels on the EU market (“methane slip”).

The German carbon management strategy will target industries with hard-to-abate process emissions that cannot be fully avoided nor directly switched to renewable electricity or hydrogen. To reduce GHG emissions in electricity generation, the German government is prioritising the rapid expansion of renewable energies, the capacity mechanism outlined in the power plant strategy, and the conversion of gas-fired power plants to hydrogen. For plants using gaseous energy sources or biomass, CCS/CCU will be applied as part of a technology-neutral transition to a climate-neutral electricity system, but subsidies will not be provided for fossil fuels. The coal phase-out will continue, and CO₂ pipeline access will be denied for emissions from coal-fired power plants. State support for CCS/CCU will focus on emissions that are difficult or impossible to avoid.

As outlined in the coalition agreement, the Federal Government will work with companies to ensure that operating licenses for fossil fuel energy infrastructure (power plants or gas pipelines) are issued in a legally

⁸⁶ [CGG. \(2024\). CGG and C-Questra sign CCUS cooperation agreement.](#)

⁸⁷ [Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz. \(2024\). Kabinett macht Weg frei für CCS in Deutschland Habeck: “Entscheidung für CCS ist Richtungsentscheidung für die Industrie in Deutschland”.](#)

secure manner, allowing them to operate beyond 2045 only if they switch to non-fossil fuels. This approach aims to prevent halting investments, stranded investments, and compensation claims.

To initiate the construction of privately run CO₂ pipelines within a state regulatory framework, the Carbon Storage Act will be updated according to the Federal Government's proposals from the 2022 evaluation report. Ambiguities in the law will be clarified, and a uniform approval system for CO₂ pipelines will be established.

The Federal Government will ratify the amendment to the London Protocol to allow CO₂ exports for offshore storage and will amend the High Seas Dumping Act accordingly. Legislation will be enacted to permit the investigation of offshore storage sites in Germany's exclusive economic zone (EEZ) and continental shelf. If sites are deemed suitable, considering safety and ecological criteria, storage facilities can be developed for industrial use. Injection of CO₂ in marine protected areas will be prohibited.

Permanent geological storage of CO₂ on German onshore territory will remain prohibited but there will be an opt-in possibility for Länder (States) to allow onshore storage.

Under the current German Carbon Dioxide Storage Act (KSpG)⁸⁸ the storage of CO₂ is only permitted in the context of demonstration projects. Maximum 4 Mt of CO₂ can be stored geologically each year. The government is reviewing the legal framework for underground storage of CO₂.

Germany's Climate Protection Plan 2050⁸⁹ underscores the necessity of CDR to achieve carbon neutrality, primarily advocating for nature-based CDR methods. The government has pledged to develop a national long-term strategy for CDR⁹⁰ and plans to adopt a Sustainable Biomass Strategy to address competition over biomass use. Furthermore, Germany has signed the Aalborg Declaration, recognising CCS/CCU as crucial technologies for facilitating the green transition and achieving net-zero emissions by 2050.

1.5.3 Potential capacity

No domestic geological CO₂ storage capacity has been identified. In theory, the Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources estimates German total storage capacity to be between 20 to 115 Gt of CO₂, mostly under the North Sea⁹¹.

1.5.4 Research, innovation, and funding

The Federal Government intends to encourage environmentally friendly technologies through CCfDs. This mechanism may also serve as an incentive for CDR methods.

⁸⁸ [Evaluierungsbericht der Bundesregierung zum Kohlendioxid-Speicherungsgesetz \(KSpG\).](#)

⁸⁹ [Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz, Bau und Reaktorsicherheit. \(2016\). Klimaschutzplan 2050 Klimaschutzpolitische Grundsätze und Ziele der Bundesregierung.](#)

⁹⁰ [Update to the long-term strategy for climate action of the Federal Republic of Germany.](#)

⁹¹ [Clean Energy Wire. \(2024\). Q&A – CCS makes comeback as Germany and the EU strive for climate neutrality.](#)

Germany updated its National Hydrogen Strategy, now allowing the possibility of supporting applications using blue hydrogen produced from fossil fuels with CCS during the ramp-up phase of the hydrogen market⁹².

Germany is active in 14 SET plan implementation working groups, including CCS/CCU.

Germany launched a EUR 50 billion programme in a bid to decarbonise its prized heavy industry⁹³.

1.5.5 Projects

GeZero Project⁹⁴: Heidelberg Materials' CCS project is set to decarbonise cement production at Geseke plant in North Rhine-Westphalia. The project aims at implementing a comprehensive CCS value chain, with the goal of capturing 700,000 tonnes of CO₂ annually from 2029. The CO₂ will be transported via ship/pipeline/rail to offshore sites in the North Sea. It has received EUR 191 million funding from the EU Innovation fund.

EVEREST Project⁹⁵: the project aims at decarbonising the limestone plant of Lhoist Germany Rheinkalk GmbH in Wülfrath, by building three oxyfuel kilns equipped with carbon capture technology. It has successfully passed preselection the Innovation Fund's third call for large-scale projects.

CO2NNECTNOW Project⁹⁶: Wintershall Dea and HES Wilhelmshaven Tank Terminal are developing a CO₂ hub. The CO₂ captured from German industrial sites will first be transported to the HES Wilhelmshaven Tank Terminal, and then transported by ship or pipeline to storage sites in the Norwegian and Danish North Sea.

H2GE Rostock Project⁹⁷: Equinor and German gas company VNG AG are evaluating options for producing low-carbon hydrogen on the Baltic Sea coast, specifically in the Rostock area, using technologies to capture, utilise, or transport and safely store CO₂ offshore.

⁹² [Kurmayer. \(2023\). Germany commits to 'blue hydrogen' in updated national strategy.](#)

⁹³ [Jones Day. \(2023\). Germany Launches EUR 50 Billion Funding Program for Decarbonization of Heavy Industry.](#)

⁹⁴ [Heidelberg Materials. \(2023\). First fully decarbonised cement plant in Germany: Heidelberg Materials gets support from the EU Innovation Fund.](#)

⁹⁵ [Lhoist. \(2023\). EU supports innovative decarbonisation of the lime industry.](#)

⁹⁶ [Wintershall Dea. \(2022\). Wintershall Dea and HES Wilhelmshaven Tank Terminal intend to jointly develop a CO₂ Hub in Wilhelmshaven.](#)

⁹⁷ [VNG AG. \(2022\). Equinor and VNG extending cooperation to hydrogen, ammonia and carbon capture.](#)

1.5.6 Bilateral agreements

Germany and Belgium: agreement to cooperate on hydrogen, carbon capture, electrification, and LNG projects as part of efforts to increase energy independence and decarbonise⁹⁸.

Germany and Denmark: declaration of intent to cooperate on the further development of CCS/CCU⁹⁹.

Germany and Norway: two joint Declaration on the cooperation in the areas of hydrogen, battery technology, offshore wind, and carbon capture and storage¹⁰⁰.

Germany's Wintershall Dea and Belgium's Fluxys have signed an agreement to jointly cooperate on a cross-border CO₂ pipeline network connecting the two countries¹⁰¹.

Wintershall Dea and Equinor have agreed to pursue the development of an extensive and safe CCS value chain connecting continental European CO₂ emitters to offshore storage sites on the Norwegian Continental Shelf¹⁰².

1.6 Hungary

1.6.1 Reduction and removal targets

The Hungarian Climate Law of 2020¹⁰³ commits Hungary to achieving net zero emissions by 2050. In line with this goal, the National Clean Development Strategy (NCDS)¹⁰⁴, developed in 2021, details the potential scenarios and steps needed to reach this target. The NCDS outlines two potential courses of action: early action (EA) and late action (LA). Both scenarios aim to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050 and the interim EU target of a 55% reduction compared to 1990 levels by 2030. However, the EA scenario is favoured by the Ministry of Innovation and Technology as it is expected to foster more growth.

The Strategy highlights the importance of CCS and CCU technologies in sectors that are difficult to decarbonise, particularly energy production and industry. It anticipates that these technologies will

⁹⁸ [Bundesregierung.de. \(2023\). Belgian-German Joint Declaration on Bilateral Cooperation on the Transition to Sustainable Carbon Neutral Economies.](#)

⁹⁹ [Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz. \(2023\). Joint declaration of intent between the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action of the Federal Republic of Germany and the Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities of Denmark on the cooperation on carbon capture utilisation and storage \(CCUS\).](#)

¹⁰⁰ [Regjeringen.no. \(2023\). Closer cooperation between Norway and Germany to develop green industry.](#)

¹⁰¹ [Fluxys. \(2023\). Fluxys, OGE and Wintershall Dea are teaming up to create a CO₂ corridor from Southern Germany to Belgium's CO₂ export hubs.](#)

¹⁰² [Wintershall Dea. \(2022\). Wintershall Dea and Equinor partner up for large-scale CCS value chain in the North Sea.](#)

¹⁰³ [Wolters Kluwer. \(2020\). 2020. évi XLIV. Törvény a klímavédelemről.](#)

¹⁰⁴ [Innovációs és Technológiai Minisztérium. \(2021\). National Clean Development Strategy 2020-2050 Executive Summary.](#)

become economically viable after 2030 due to the availability of cheaper abatement alternatives and the current early development stage of many CCS/CCU technologies. By 2050, CCS could capture between 3 and 7 Mt of CO₂ in the industry and energy sectors, respectively. BECCS is expected to play a significant role, particularly after 2040, and further research and development in this area is deemed necessary.

1.6.2 Legal framework

The Hungarian Parliament passed the 2020 Climate Law¹⁰⁵, committing the country to achieving net zero emissions by 2050. This law also requires the government to develop short-, middle-, and long-term climate strategies. Additionally, it sets a goal of reducing GHG emissions by 40% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels.

The geological storage of CO₂ is regulated by the Oversight Authority of Regulated Activities decree 29/2022. (I. 31.)¹⁰⁶. The Mining Authority is responsible for surveying potential geological storage sites every five years and publishing the results on its website. Stakeholders wishing to store CO₂ in geological formations must conduct research and apply for a permit from the Mining Authority, making the process more complex.

1.6.3 Potential capacity

Hungary could store 97 Mt of CO₂ in depleted oil and gas reservoirs, and potentially up to 750 Mt in deep saline aquifers¹⁰⁷. This storage capacity means that besides storing its own CO₂ emissions, Hungary could provide storage for other countries, an opportunity which should be addressed by the government or market participants. One such market participant is the integrated oil company, that already plans on developing a potential 70 Mt of storage in the region by 2026, including for third parties.

1.6.4 Research, innovation, and funding

The NCDS states that R&D and innovation are necessary elements in achieving net zero emissions by 2020¹⁰⁸. It mentions CCS and CCU in the energy sector and industry, using specific agricultural practices to speed up the absorption of CO₂ in soils, and forestry as specific areas where innovative technologies could be used. It emphasises the government's role in encouraging private-sector green innovation. To support this role, the New National Research, Development and Innovation Strategy 2021-2030¹⁰⁹ was developed,

¹⁰⁵ [Wolters Kluwer. \(2020\). 2020. évi XLIV. Törvény a klímavédelemről.](#)

¹⁰⁶ [Wolters Kluwer. \(2022\). 29/2022. \(I. 31.\) SZTFH rendelet az energetikai és ipari eredetű szén-dioxid tárolására alkalmas földtani szerkezetekkel kapcsolatos részletes szabályokról.](#)

¹⁰⁷ [Bartovic et al. \(n.d.\) Building momentum for the long-term CCS deployment in the CEE region: assessment of current state, past experiences and potential for CCS deployment in the CEE region.](#)

¹⁰⁸ [Innovációs és Technológiai Minisztérium. \(2021\). National Clean Development Strategy 2020-2050 Executive Summary.](#)

¹⁰⁹ [National Research, Development and Innovation Office. \(2021\). Proposal on the Research, Development and Innovation Strategy of Hungary \(2021-2030\).](#)

which emphasises the need for green investment and circular economy but makes no specific mention of CCS or CDR technologies.

No specific funding mechanisms for CCS/CCU have been identified.

1.6.5 Projects

Hungary has no large-scale CCS projects in operation, however, it is preparing to launch a pilot CCS programme at Pannonia Bio Zrt, a bio-refinery which initially specialised in bio-ethanol production¹¹⁰. The facility has evolved into a hub for a variety of bio-based technologies, including nutrition, health, biochemical, and fuel bioproducts that can serve as eco-friendly alternatives to fossil-based materials.

1.6.6 Bilateral agreements

No bilateral agreements have been identified.

1.7 Italy

1.7.1 Reduction and removal targets

Italy's Long-Term Strategy¹¹¹ sets a goal of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050. To achieve this, it plans to compensate for approximately 20 to 40 Mt of CO₂ emissions using CCS and CDR technologies. The strategy highlights the potential of BECCS and DACCS for achieving negative emissions. Fire-fighting and sustainable soil management policies will be used to remove 45 Mt of CO₂ annually by 2050. However, there are no binding targets set for CCS/CCU or CDR.

1.7.2 Legal framework

Storage is permitted under Legislative Decree 162/2011¹¹², which provides a legal framework for geological CO₂ storage, identifying the competent authority and outlining monitoring and reporting obligations. The regulatory framework is currently being revised to accelerate the authorisation process, define technical requirements for transport and storage, and establish the business model for CCS.

¹¹⁰ [Doneva. \(2023\). Hungary prepares to launch carbon capture and storage pilot.](#)

¹¹¹ [Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare, Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico, Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti, Ministero delle Politiche agricole, Alimentari e Forestali. \(2021\). Strategia Italiana di lungo termine sulla riduzione delle emissioni dei gas a effetto serra.](#)

¹¹² [Decreto Legislativo 14 settembre 2011, n. 162. Attuazione della direttiva 2009/31/CE in materia di stoccaggio geologico del biossido di carbonio, nonché modifica delle direttive 85/337/CEE, 2000/60/CE, 2001/80/CE, 2004/35/CE, 2006/12/CE, 2008/1/CE e del Regolamento \(CE\) n. 1013/2006. \(11G0207\).](#)

1.7.3 Potential capacity

The draft updated NECP¹¹³ outlines an ongoing analysis of the storage potential in depleted oil and gas fields, primarily those operated by Eni. The analysis suggests a potential storage capacity of around 750 Mt of CO₂. Additionally, the plan proposes the use of saline aquifers, potentially expanding the total storage capacity to 5,000 Mt of CO₂. Despite these considerations, the draft NECP lacks clarity on the timeline for the availability of CO₂ storage capacity and does not provide projections for annual injection capacity by 2030.

The draft updated NECP refers to plans for the deployment of cross-border dedicated CO₂ transport capacities of up to 4.6 Mtpa to be captured mainly in France and Italy and transported for storage in Italy as part of the Callisto project.

1.7.4 Research, innovation, and funding

The HERCCULES project focuses on developing innovative CCS technologies, demonstrating the complete CCS value chain in Italy and Greece. The project involves collaboration among multiple stakeholders including research institutions, industrial partners, and governmental bodies to achieve its objectives of mitigating climate change impacts through advanced CO₂ management strategies¹¹⁴. The project receives EUR 29.6 million in EU funding (total of EUR 39.6 million) for a duration of 60 months starting 1 January 2023.

The ECCSELLENT project aims to update and enhance CCS/CCU facilities across Italy through the ECCSEL Research Infrastructure¹¹⁵. It focuses on improving infrastructure and capabilities to support research and development in CCS/CCU technologies.

The draft updated NECP details the potential for regional cooperation in R&I on CCS/CCU through important projects of common European interest (IPCEI). Together with France and Greece, Italy is planning to support the development of CCS infrastructure within the scope of the Trans-European Network for Energy (TEN-E) Regulation, and promote cross-border cooperation on CO₂ capture, transport, and storage, through the development of joint projects and plans for cross-border management of CCS. Expressions of interest for injection in Italy have been received from foreign emitters totalling over 1 Mtpa of CO₂ (mainly from France) in addition to those relating to national installations of at least 3.6 Mtpa. Italian volumes of CO₂ are also expected to be exported to other storage sites in the Mediterranean basin, in particular to Greece.

¹¹³ [European Commission. \(2023\). Italy - Draft Updated NECP 2021-2030.](#)

¹¹⁴ [Herccules. \(n.d.\). Decarbonising with CCUS.](#)

¹¹⁵ [ECCSEL ERIC. \(2022\). A new project for updating Italian CCUS facilities.](#)

No dedicated national funding explicitly aimed at CCS or CDR technologies has been identified. However, the Fund for Sustainable Growth¹¹⁶ and the National Plan for Recovery and Resilience¹¹⁷ might serve as potential sources of funding for CCS or CDR projects.

1.7.5 Projects

Snam has announced an increased investment of EUR 11.5 billion by 2027 to bolster infrastructure in support of the Italian energy transition¹¹⁸. This investment, which represents a 15% increase from its previous plan, will support the development of a CCS hub offshore Ravenna in collaboration with Eni. The project aims to contribute to Italy's carbon neutrality goals and includes constructing new pipelines and finalising LNG infrastructure, all while gearing up for potential hydrogen integration.

Italgas and Buzzi Unicem have signed an agreement to explore the feasibility of power to gas plants combined with carbon capture systems at Buzzi Unicem's Augusta cement plant¹¹⁹. This initiative aims to decarbonise their production processes by producing synthetic methane using green hydrogen and captured CO₂.

CCS Ravenna Hub¹²⁰: operated by Eni in partnership with the Italian utility Snam, this project aims to inject captured emissions into a depleted offshore gas field near Ravenna. Initially focusing on emissions from Eni's local natural gas treatment plant, the project has also signed a letter of intent with five nearby hard-to-abate industries. By 2030, the hub could store up to 10 Mtpa of CO₂. It is expected to be operational in 2024.

The **CALLISTO (CARbon Liquefaction transportation and STORAGE) Mediterranean CO₂ Network project**: aims to develop the largest open-access multi-modal CO₂ hub in the Mediterranean, supported by dedicated onshore transport infrastructures¹²¹. This initiative seeks to enable the decarbonisation of various industrial emitter clusters through CO₂ capture, aggregation, transportation, and permanent storage, while preserving production levels in energy-intensive industries in the region.

¹¹⁶ [Contributi PMI. \(n.d.\). Fondo Per La Crescita Sostenibile: Bandi E Interventi.](#)

¹¹⁷ [Ministero dell'Economia e delle Finanze. \(2021\). The Recovery and Resilience Plan: Next Generation Italia.](#)

¹¹⁸ [Stankova. \(2024\). Italy's Snam to Invest \\$12.5B By 2027 To Boost Gas Infrastructure With Carbon Capture Included.](#)

¹¹⁹ [Buzzi Unicem. \(2022\). Italgas and Buzzi Unicem sign an agreement to study the feasibility of Power to Gas plants to decarbonize cement production processes.](#)

¹²⁰ [Ravenna CCS. Our activities in Ravenna.](#)

¹²¹ [Snam. \(2023\). Snam: SouthH2 Corridor and Callisto Mediterranean CO₂ Network enter the 6th List of EU Projects of Common Interest \(PCI\).](#)

The project joined the sixth PCI list¹²² and includes the collection and transportation of CO₂ both onshore, via existing or new pipelines, and offshore via shipping from emitters in Italy and France. Relevant CO₂ regasification and liquefaction hubs located in Italy and France will prepare the CO₂ for final storage at the Ravenna CCS Hub in Italy.

Expected to become operational in 2027, this project is coordinated by Air Liquide and promoted by 18 companies, including Snam and Eni, the operator of the Ravenna CCS Hub. It aims to reduce emissions by enabling the transport and geological storage of captured CO₂ from industrial emission points to an offshore storage site managed by Eni, with a capacity estimated at 500 Mt of CO₂. The first injections are set to start in early 2024.

Throughout the PCI selection process, the project gained support from both Italy and France. The cooperation between these countries in designing a common CCS strategy was confirmed in March 2023 with the issuance of the Mediterranean CCS Plan, signed by both governments. This plan supports the development of the first CCS project in the Mediterranean Basin, the Callisto Mediterranean CO₂ Network Project, and promotes further CCS projects in the region.

Limenet¹²³: transforms CO₂ from the atmosphere or other sources into an aqueous solution of calcium bicarbonates using calcium carbonate, marine water, and renewable electric energy. This method provides durable and stable CO₂ storage in seas and oceans. Additionally, by dissolving carbonate compounds in seawater, it increases alkalinity, enhancing the ocean's capacity to resist changes in acidity levels, which can benefit marine life.

STORE&GO Project¹²⁴: Climeworks has launched a second-generation direct air capture plant (DAC-3) in Troia Italy as part of the Horizon 2020 research project STORE&GO. The plant will filter up to 150 tons of CO₂ from ambient air per year and will be used as a key resource to produce carbon-neutral fuel (Power-to-Gas).

1.7.6 Bilateral agreements

No bilateral agreements identified. However, Italy has expressed its support for regional collaboration with France and Greece to facilitate the development of CCS infrastructure in the Mediterranean Sea basin.

¹²² [European Commission. \(2023\). Annex to the Commission delegated regulation \(EU\) amending regulation \(EU\) no 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the Union list of projects of common interest and projects of mutual interest.](#)

¹²³ [Limenet.](#)

¹²⁴ [Store&Go.](#)

1.8 Norway

1.8.1 Reduction and removal targets

Norway's Climate Action Plan 2021-2030¹²⁵ sets a 50% to 55% GHG emission reduction target for 2030. The Plan also highlights a voluntary agreement¹²⁶ between the Norwegian government and national agricultural organisations, which commits to reducing emissions and enhancing removals in the agricultural sector by 5 Mt of GHG emissions over the period from 2021 to 2030.

The Norwegian Environmental Agency, part of the Ministry of Climate and Environment, has recently proposed innovative incentives for CDR¹²⁷. These recommendations include implementing a reversed CO₂ tax and offering monetary rewards for each tonne of CO₂ removed. They also suggest combining a national CDR policy with the option to trade CDR credits on the voluntary carbon market. The agency's report estimates that by 2030, DACCS could contribute 1 Mt of CO₂ annually, and bio-CCS, including BECCS, could contribute an additional 1.5 Mt, aiming for a 55% reduction¹²⁸.

Historically, the forestry sector in Norway has played a significant role in LULUCF-based removals, serving as the country's predominant greenhouse gas sink.

1.8.2 Legal framework

Norway's Climate Change Act¹²⁹ targets a 50% to 55% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030 compared to 1990 levels, and aims for a 90% to 95% reduction by 2050. While the Act does not explicitly establish a net-zero target, it aspires for Norway to become a low-emission society by 2050.

Norway was among the first to ratify the amendment to the London Protocol, which permits CO₂ storage in the seabed, and has urged other European nations to follow suit.

1.8.3 Potential capacity

A Norwegian CO₂ storage atlas describing possible subsurface storage locations in the Norwegian part of the North Sea, prepared by the Norwegian Petroleum Directorate, indicates that this area has a total storage capacity of about 70 Gt of CO₂¹³⁰.

¹²⁵ [Regjeringen.no. \(2021\). Norway's Climate Action Plan for 2021–2030 — Meld. St. 13 \(2020–2021\) Report to the Storting \(white paper\).](#)

¹²⁶ [Norges Bondelag. \(2019\). Inngår klimaavtale for jordbruket.](#)

¹²⁷ [Miljødirektoratet. \(2023\). Industrien kan fjerne CO₂ med nye virkemidler.](#)

¹²⁸ [Miljødirektoratet. \(2023\). Klimatiltak i Norge mot 2030: Oppdatert kunnskapsgrunnlag om utslippsreduksjonspotensial, barrierer og mulige virkemidler - 2023](#)

¹²⁹ [Klima- og miljødepartementet. \(2021\). Lov om endringer i klimaloven \(klimamål for 2030 og 2050\).](#)

¹³⁰ [Norwegian Offshore Directorate. \(2022\). CO₂ storage Atlas Norwegian North Sea.](#)

1.8.4 Research, innovation, and funding

Norway has multiple R&D and innovation support programmes dedicated to CCS. To some extent, these also support CCS-based CDR methods, such as DACCS and bio-CCS, which includes BECCS. Other conventional CDR methods also receive targeted support.

Norway has announced the creation of gigaCCS, a new R&I centre dedicated to advancing CCS on a gigatonne scale. Funded with NOK 180 million and operational from 2025 to 2032, gigaCCS aims to develop competitive CCS technologies, support industry and societal needs, and train specialists through collaborations with over 70 R&D and industry partners¹³¹. The centre will build on the successes of its predecessor, the Norwegian CCS Research Centre (NCCS).

Starting January 1, 2023, facilities utilising CO₂ capture and storage are exempt from the national CO₂ tax¹³². This exemption is facilitated through refunds for CO₂ taxes paid on mineral oil, petrol, natural gas, and liquefied petroleum gas, provided the CO₂ emissions are captured and stored. Waste incineration plants that implement CCS can also receive a tax exemption from the Norwegian waste incineration tax on fossil CO₂ emissions.

1.8.5 Projects

Norway is at the forefront of CCS development, with several ongoing projects aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Some notable CCS projects in Norway include:

Longship Project¹³³: the Longship project is one of the most significant CCS initiatives in Norway and Europe. It involves capturing CO₂ emissions from industrial facilities and transporting them via pipelines to be permanently stored offshore beneath the North Sea. The start of the execution phase of the Longship project is due at the start of 2025. The project includes the following key components:

- **Northern Lights**¹³⁴: this is the transport and storage part of the Longship project, operated by Equinor, Shell, and Total. It aims to establish a CCS infrastructure for transporting CO₂ from industrial sites to offshore storage sites.
- **CO₂ Capture Facilities**: the Longship project includes funding for the development of CO₂ capture facilities at industrial sites, such as the Fortum Oslo Varme waste-to-energy plant and Norcem's cement factory in Brevik.

Sleipner¹³⁵: this project, operated by Equinor, has been in operation since 1996 and involves capturing CO₂ produced from natural gas processing at the Sleipner field in the North Sea. The captured CO₂ is injected into a deep saline aquifer for storage.

¹³¹ [NCCS. \(2024\). New Research Centre Announced Dedicated to the Realisation of Gigatonne CCS.](#)

¹³² [The Norwegian Tax Administration. \(n.d.\). Mineral product tax.](#)

¹³³ [Gassnova. \(n.d.\). The Longship CCS Project.](#)

¹³⁴ [Northern Lights. \(n.d.\). About the Longship project.](#)

¹³⁵ [Vattenfall. \(2024\). Norway's Sleipner: Where CO₂ has been buried in the rock since 1996.](#)

Snøhvit¹³⁶: Equinor's Snøhvit LNG plant in the Barents Sea has been capturing and storing CO₂ since 2008. The captured CO₂ is injected into a subsea reservoir.

1.8.6 Bilateral agreements

Norway and Belgium: negotiations for a bilateral agreement on the cross-border transport and storage of CO₂ on the Norwegian Continental Shelf, under the London Protocol¹³⁷.

Norway and Denmark: MoU to strengthen cooperation in the field of the energy transition in the North Sea, with a special emphasis on CCS/CCU, offshore wind, related offshore grid infrastructure and hydrogen¹³⁸.

Norway and Germany: two joint Declaration on the cooperation in the areas of hydrogen, battery technology, offshore wind, and carbon capture and storage¹³⁹.

Norway and Switzerland: signed a declaration of intent to strengthen cooperation related to CCS and CDR¹⁴⁰.

Norway and Sweden: announced their intentions to sign an agreement, enabling the transportation of CO₂ from Sweden to Norway¹⁴¹.

Norway and the Netherlands: signed a MoU to strengthen cooperation in the field of CCS¹⁴².

Norway and the UK: signed a MoU to strengthen cooperation in the field of CCS¹⁴³.

¹³⁶ [Norwegian Offshore Directorate. \(n.d.\). Storage capacity Snøhvit area.](#)

¹³⁷ [Regjeringen.no. \(2023\). Belgium and Norway will work closer on cross-border transport and storage of CO₂.](#)

¹³⁸ [Memorandum of understanding between the Ministry of Petroleum and Energy of Norway and the Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities of Denmark on energy cooperation in the North Sea.](#)

¹³⁹ [Regjeringen.no. \(2023\). Closer cooperation between Norway and Germany to develop green industry.](#)

¹⁴⁰ [Regjeringen.no. \(2024\). Strengthened cooperation between Norway and Switzerland on CCS and CDR.](#)

¹⁴¹ [Sveriges geologiska undersökning. \(2022\). Nytt avtal ska göra det möjligt att lagra svensk koldioxid i Norge.](#)

¹⁴² [Memorandum of understanding to promote bilateral cooperation in the field of carbon capture and storage \(CCS\), and exploring future areas of energy cooperation related to the North Sea.](#)

¹⁴³ [Memorandum of understanding between the Ministry of Petroleum and Energy of the Government of Norway and the Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy of the Government of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland on cooperation in the field of carbon capture usage and storage.](#)

1.9 Spain

1.9.1 Reduction and removal targets

There are no binding targets on CCS/CCU or CDR, however, Spain's Long-Term Climate Strategy (ELP 2050)¹⁴⁴ seeks to reduce emissions by 90% by 2050, with natural carbon sinks absorbing the remainder (at least 37 Mt of CO₂ per year by 2050). This target is expected to be achieved through extensive reforestation, wetland restoration, and agroforestry systems. Measures outlined in the ELP 2050 aim to meet the climate neutrality scenario through:

- a reforestation rate of 20,000 hectares/year until 2050, which would increase absorption by 7 MtCO₂e a year.
- a restoration of 50,000 hectares of wetlands, which will add another projected 1 MtCO₂e per year to the sink capacity.
- agroforestry systems and meadow regeneration which will further augment the sink capacity by 0.5 MtCO₂e per year.

1.9.2 Legal framework

CO₂ Storage is allowed in Spain. Spain has not ratified Article 6 of the London Protocol on cross-border transport of CO₂. The updated draft NECP¹⁴⁵ includes measures that have the potential to shape the future role of CDR in the following ways: industrial decarbonisation, informing research priorities, and allocating funding for measures to protect Spanish ecosystems.

The Strategic Projects for Economic Recovery and Transformation (PERTE)¹⁴⁶ for industrial decarbonisation is linked to Spain's Recovery and Resilience Plan¹⁴⁷ and mentions carbon removals in the context of applying BECCS.

Spain's 2021 Climate Law (Ley 7/2021 de cambio climático y transición energética)¹⁴⁸ designates a net zero target by 2050. Article 26 of this Law recommends that public entities incentivise citizens and private actors to increase the capacity of capturing CO₂ in ecosystem carbon sinks, with emphasis largely on actors in the LULUCF sector.

¹⁴⁴ [Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico. \(2020\). Estrategia de descarbonización a largo plazo 2050.](#)

¹⁴⁵ [European Commission. \(2023\). Spain - Draft Updated NECP 2021-2030.](#)

¹⁴⁶ [España Digital. \(n.d.\). PERTE: Strategic Projects for Economic Recovery and Transformation.](#)

¹⁴⁷ [Gobierno de España. \(2023\). Segunda fase del plan de recuperación, transformación y resiliencia del reino de España.](#)

¹⁴⁸ [Boletín Oficial del Estado. \(2021\). Ley 7/2021, de 20 de mayo, de cambio climático y transición energética.](#)

1.9.3 Potential capacity

The draft updated NECP does not provide any concrete estimation of geological CO₂ storage capacity and does not foresee the deployment of dedicated CO₂ transport capacity.

In a 2023 report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on Implementation of Directive 2009/31/EC on the geological storage of carbon dioxide¹⁴⁹, Spain explicitly mentioned their entire territory as potential storage sites.

There is potential for developing BECCS in Spain since biogas features prominently in Spain's EPL 2050. Capturing and storing this CO₂ stream could play a role in addressing emissions from sectors using biomethane as an energy source.

1.9.4 Research, innovation, and funding

The Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)¹⁵⁰ developed patents for CO₂ carbonation-calcination at the La Pereda pilot plant. A variant of this process was developed in parallel at a 400kW pilot plant at the La Robla thermal power plant, which could be used for BECCS processes.

The Spanish CO₂ Technology Platform (PTECO₂) promotes the development and implementation of CCS/CCU technologies in Spain by fostering research and innovation, providing training and educational resources, and facilitating collaboration between scientific, technological, and industrial communities¹⁵¹. PTECO₂ aims to help Spain meet its emission reduction commitments and advance a competitive CO₂ sector through various projects, regulatory support, and public engagement.

CaLby2030 is a European project funded under the Horizon Europe framework, aiming to achieve commercial deployment of calcium looping technology for carbon capture by 2030¹⁵². Using Circulating Fluidised Bed reactors, the project will demonstrate over 99% CO₂ capture rates in the cement, steel, and waste-to-energy sectors through pilot plants in Germany, Sweden, and Spain. The project, coordinated by CSIC, involves 18 partners and has a budget of over EUR 15 million.

The Council has coordinated a project funded by Horizon 2020, focused on developing the geochemical carbon dioxide removal potential of Spain through enhanced weathering and carbonation strategies for mine wastes to sequester more CO₂¹⁵³.

¹⁴⁹ [European Commission. \(2023\). Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on implementation of directive 2009/31/EC on the geological storage of carbon dioxide.](#)

¹⁵⁰ [Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas.](#)

¹⁵¹ [Plataforma Tecnológica Española del CO₂. \(n.d.\) PTECO₂.](#)

¹⁵² [CaLby2030. \(n.d.\). Decarbonising industrial processes with Calcium Looping.](#)

¹⁵³ [CORDIS. \(2021\). Developing enhanced weathering methods in mine tailings for CO₂ sequestration.](#)

The Innovation Fund's latest call for large-scale projects¹⁵⁴ selected to fund the Green Meiga project, which provides an integrated approach to e-methanol production through direct air capture in an advanced CO₂ capture system.

FES-CO₂ (a.k.a. Carbon Fund)¹⁵⁵ is a public fund created in Spain under the framework of the Kyoto Protocol to help achieve the country's GHG emissions reduction targets. Managed by the Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, the fund supports projects that help to reduce CO₂ emissions in Spain. In 2021, the fund provided EUR 30 million to projects reducing CO₂ emissions.

1.9.5 Projects

Lighthouse Carboneras Project¹⁵⁶ (joint venture by Carbon Clean and LafargeHolcim): aims to capture CO₂ emitted through the cement production process to be further transformed, cleaned, and reused locally. The CO₂ will be captured from the cement plant's flue gas and will be recycled for agricultural use for accelerated crop production. By imitating and accelerating the natural photosynthesis process, this technique has the potential to increase farm efficiency by reducing water and soil ratio per kilogram of vegetable production. Starting with 10% of CO₂ emissions from 2022, the commercial applicability of this viable circular carbon economy business model can potentially leverage 700,000 tonnes of CO₂ and achieve 100% decarbonisation at the plant.

PilotSTRATEGY Project¹⁵⁷: funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, the project is investigating geological CO₂ storage sites in industrial regions of Southern and Eastern Europe to support development of large-scale CCS. Research is focussing on deep saline aquifers—porous rock formations filled with brine several kilometres below ground, which promise a large capacity for storing CO₂ captured from clusters of industry. This project is funded by the European Innovation Fund.

Green Meiga Project¹⁵⁸ (Green Methanol in Galicia): e-methanol plant developed by Iberdrola that will use a combination of PEM, solid oxide, and alkaline electrolyzers, as well as both enzyme-based and direct air carbon-capture technologies. This project is funded by the European Innovation Fund (approximately EUR 123 million).

Tarragona Network Hydrogen Project¹⁵⁹: pressurised alkaline electrolyser project developed by Repsol, which will sell both renewable hydrogen and by-product oxygen to off-takers. This project is funded by the European Innovation Fund (approximately EUR 62 million).

¹⁵⁴ [European Commission. \(2022\). Large-scale calls.](#)

¹⁵⁵ [Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico. \(n.d.\). Fondo de Carbono FES-CO₂.](#)

¹⁵⁶ [LafargeHolcim. \(2022\). "Lighthouse project", LafargeHolcim España.](#)

¹⁵⁷ [Dütschke et al. \(2022\). Community Acceptance: findings from community profiles and first local survey.](#)

¹⁵⁸ [European Commission. \(2024\). Green Meiga: green methanol in Galicia.](#)

¹⁵⁹ [Catalonia Trade & Investment. \(2022\). Tarragona will have the largest green hydrogen plant in Spain with an investment of 230 million euros.](#)

Triskelion Project¹⁶⁰: green methanol facility in Spain developed by chemicals and power producer Forestal del Atlántico, based on green hydrogen and captured carbon from an existing combined heat and power plant. Triskelion will also liquefy, and store oxygen produced during electrolysis (operational by 2027). This project is funded by the European Innovation Fund (approximately EUR 49 million).

Asturias H2 Valley Project¹⁶¹: developed by EDP subsidiary, H2 Aboño is a renewable hydrogen facility that will be located inside an existing coal power plant in Spain. This project is funded by the European Innovation Fund (approximately EUR 39 million).

1.9.6 Bilateral agreements

Spain and the UK: environmental MoU¹⁶² on Gibraltar, establishing the principle of cooperation for ensuring the highest standards of protection throughout the area, with the result that this will have an impact on such issues as solid and liquid waste management, the control of fuel supply to ships, and scientific research including marine research using specific ships for that purpose.

1.10 Sweden

1.10.1 Reduction and removal targets

Sweden aims to achieve carbon neutrality by 2045. The target requires a minimum emissions reduction of 85% compared to 1990 levels with the remaining 15% to be met through supplementary measures, including CDR.

A 2020 public inquiry¹⁶³ proposed that BECCS could contribute up to 1.8 MtCO₂ annually by 2030 and, approximately, 3 to 10 MtCO₂ per year by 2045.

The draft updated NECP provides intermediate targets for GHG emissions¹⁶⁴:

- By 2030, GHG emissions in Sweden in the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR) sector should be at least 63% lower than those in 1990. No more than 8 percentage points of emission reductions may be achieved through accompanying measures (such as BECCS).
- By 2030, GHG emissions from domestic transport, excluding domestic flights included in the EU ETS, should be at least 70% lower compared to 2010.

¹⁶⁰ [Triskelion green methanol plant.](#)

¹⁶¹ [European Commission. \(2024\). Asturias H2 Valley.](#)

¹⁶² [Memorando de entendimiento sobre cooperación en materia medioambiental.](#)

¹⁶³ [Regeringskansliet. \(2020\). Vägen till en klimatpositiv framtid.](#)

¹⁶⁴ [European Commission. \(2023\). Sweden - Draft Updated NECP 2021-2030.](#)

- By 2040, GHG emissions in Sweden in the ESR sector should be at least 75% lower than those in 1990. No more than 2 percentage points of emission reductions may be achieved through accompanying measures.

The target also includes the potential additional net uptake of GHG as a result of policy interventions in the forest and LULUCF sector.

1.10.2 Legal framework

CO₂ storage is permitted in Sweden, though no geological CO₂ storage capacity has yet been identified. The draft update NECP notes that work on a CCS and bio-CCS strategy began in 2023. According to this plan, CCS may be used to achieve Sweden's 2045 emissions target if no other alternatives are available.

Sweden has ratified Article 6 of the London Protocol, allowing for the cross-border transport of CO₂.

Regarding carbon removal, the Swedish Energy Agency has proposed that entities receiving state support for BECCS should be able to sell carbon removal credits on a voluntary market. The agency aims to establish this market and gradually phase out state support. The tonnes of CO₂ removed within Swedish territory will count towards national mitigation targets, with private buyers being informed that their purchases contribute to Sweden's targets.

Sweden has also signed the Aalborg Declaration, which identifies CCS and CCU as crucial technologies for supporting the green transition and achieving net-zero emissions by 2050. Additionally, Sweden plans to utilise Article 6 of the Paris Agreement to potentially offset part of its residual emissions as part of its supplementary measures package.

1.10.3 Potential capacity

The Swedish Geological Survey has the responsibility of identifying suitable locations for geological carbon dioxide storage in Sweden. While no geological CO₂ storage capacity has yet been, assessments highlight two potential areas of interest, the south-east Baltic Sea and south-west Skåne.

1.10.4 Research, innovation, and funding

Sweden supports CCS and CDR research and development through the Industrial Leap initiative¹⁶⁵. The initiative comprises a total of SEK 1 354 million in 2023 and funds projects that run until 2030. Approximately 30 CDR projects have received support, including feasibility studies for BECCS and R&D for other methods like DACCS.

The public inquiry in Sweden identified biochar as a potentially promising solution for CDR. However, it was determined that additional state support beyond the funding provided by the Leap initiative was not suitable. This decision was based on the requirement for further applied research to understand how biochar could effectively contribute to meeting Sweden's mitigation targets.

¹⁶⁵ [Swedish Energy Agency. \(2023\). The Industrial Leap.](#)

Sweden is active in many SET-Plan Implementation Working Groups, including CCS/CCU.

The Industrial Leap¹⁶⁶ provides support for carbon removal research and development. The Government allocated an additional SEK 600 million per year from 2023 to 2025 and a mandate frame of SEK 5.2 billion for 2024 to 2030. This includes support for CDR technologies.

The Swedish government will allocate SEK 36 billion during the period 2026–2046, which will be distributed to the actors who can capture and store carbon dioxide at the lowest cost¹⁶⁷.

The Ministry of Finance proposes reducing the electricity tax to a minimum level for negative emissions projects, subjecting them to a lower rate of EUR 0.055 cents per kilowatt hour¹⁶⁸.

A specific call in 2020 is allocating EUR 4.5 million per year until 2027 for research and innovation in negative emissions.

The Swedish Energy Agency will hold the reverse auctions to provide economic support to actors who have submitted the winning bids. The reverse auction for BECCS is expected to commence six months after the Commission announces its decision on allowing Sweden to give state aid to national companies for verified geologically stored biogenic CO₂¹⁶⁹.

1.10.5 Projects

Cementa Slite Plant Project¹⁷⁰: the HeidelbergCement Group develops the world's first carbon-neutral cement plant in Slite, which should capture up to 1.8 Mt of CO₂ annually once fully operational.

BECCS Stockholm Project¹⁷¹: by developing a full-scale BECCS-plant connected to its existing biomass CHP (Combined Heat and Power) plant KVV8, the project aims at capturing and storing up to 800 000 tons of biogenic CO₂ per year, and further improve the technology in the future. The project is supported by the EU's Innovation Fund and received EUR 180 million in EU funding.

Preem CCS Project¹⁷²: collaboration between Preem, Aker Carbon Capture, SINTEF Energy Research, Chalmers University of Technology, and Equinor to develop CO₂ capture from the Preem refineries in Sweden, and subsequent ship transport of captured CO₂ for permanent storage on the Norwegian Continental Shelf.

¹⁶⁶ Ibid.

¹⁶⁷ [Regeringskansliet. \(2022\). Stor satsning görs på infångning av biogen koldioxid.](#)

¹⁶⁸ [Regeringskansliet. \(2023\). Befrielse från energiskatt på el för infångning av koldioxid.](#)

¹⁶⁹ [Energimyndigheten. \(2023\). CCS – Carbon Capture and Storage.](#)

¹⁷⁰ [Heidelberg Materials. \(2021\). Sweden first in the world with carbon-neutral cement plant.](#)

¹⁷¹ [Stockholm Exergi. \(n.d.\). BECCS - Negative emissions.](#)

¹⁷² [Biermann et al. \(2022\). Preem CCS: Synthesis of main project findings and insights.](#)

1.10.6 Bilateral agreements

Sweden and Norway: announced their intentions to sign an agreement, enabling the transportation of CO₂ from Sweden to Norway¹⁷³.

Vattenfall has signed a Memorandum of Understanding with Norwegian Aker Carbon Capture to accelerate the evaluation of future carbon capture plants in Sweden and Northern Europe¹⁷⁴.

1.11 The Netherlands

1.11.1 Reduction and removal targets

The Dutch Climate Act¹⁷⁵ targets a 55% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030, aiming for net zero by 2050 and negative emissions thereafter. The Dutch Climate Agreement¹⁷⁶, detailed in the Dutch Climate Plan 2021-2030¹⁷⁷, aims to cut emissions by 14.3 Mtpa by 2030, with BECCS in electricity generation projected to reduce net emissions by 1 Mt of CO₂. While there are no binding targets for CCS or CDR, CCS/CCU are expected to play a significant role in achieving a target of CO₂ reduction of 20 Mt in the manufacturing sector by 2030.

1.11.2 Legal framework

The Dutch Long-Term Strategy¹⁷⁸ includes CCS and biomass as key components of climate policy, highlighting the importance of negative emissions through soil carbon sequestration, afforestation, and BECCS. CO₂ storage and transport are permitted, with the Netherlands ratifying Article 6 of the London Protocol on cross-border CO₂ transport. The government is developing a CDR Roadmap and has signed the Aalborg Declaration, recognising CCS/CCU as essential for achieving net-zero emissions by 2050.

The CO₂ tax¹⁷⁹ for the Dutch industry is one of the main tools introduced to bring down industrial GHG emissions. It started at EUR 30 per tonne of CO₂ in 2021 and will rise to EUR 125 per tonne in 2030. If the price of the EU ETS is lower than the price set by the tax, the difference between the two needs to be paid. However, the tax only applies to CO₂ emissions above the EU-ETS benchmarks.

¹⁷³ [Sveriges geologiska undersökning. \(2022\). Nytt avtal ska göra det möjligt att lagra svensk koldioxid i Norge.](#)

¹⁷⁴ [Vattenfall. \(2020\). Vattenfall and Aker Carbon Capture to achieve negative emissions in bio CCS-projects.](#)

¹⁷⁵ [Overheid.nl. \(2023\). Klimaatwet.](#)

¹⁷⁶ [Klimaatakkoord. \(2019\). National Climate Agreement - The Netherlands.](#)

¹⁷⁷ [Ministerie van Economische Zaken. \(2020\). Klimaatplan 2021-2030.](#)

¹⁷⁸ [Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy. \(2019\). Long term strategy on climate mitigation.](#)

¹⁷⁹ [Nederlandse Emissieautoriteit. CO₂-heffing industrie.](#)

1.11.3 Potential capacity

The draft updated NECP mentions no indicative CO₂ storage capacity, however based on public announced industry initiatives 10 Mtpa injection capacity is expected to be made available to the market by 2030¹⁸⁰.

In terms of the potential of different CDR methods in the Netherlands, biochar-based solutions are expected to play only a small role, due to the highly optimised usage of biomass waste streams. The biggest potential lies for BECCS, mostly from the waste incineration sector. Retrofitting coal energy plants to biomass combined with CCS could also play a role, although the availability of biomass would need to be assessed.

1.11.4 Research, innovation, and funding

Integrated Knowledge and Innovation Agendas¹⁸¹ has been developed to provide a long-term vision for research priorities, including CDR which mentioned several times as a means of achieving negative emissions. The draft updated NECP¹⁸² identifies 13 key research streams, some of which are related to CDR and CCS development. The University of Twente has a dedicated research stream on negative emission technologies, with six different research programmes.

The **Stimulating Sustainable Energy Production and Climate Transition scheme (SDE++)**¹⁸³: provides subsidies to companies and non-profit organisations that produce large-scale renewable energy or reduce CO₂ emissions. It bridges the financial gap between EU ETS pricing and CCS project construction and operation costs, covering CO₂ capture, transport, and storage. The subsidy cap on CCS was eliminated in 2023, but eligibility is limited to CO₂ storage in Dutch gas fields and the Dutch continental shelf. Only CCS for industrial purposes is eligible for the subsidy. The subsidy is granted to the owner of the capture installation, but also includes an amount for the transport and storage costs that can be paid to a third party. The Dutch government has continued to reward early deployment of CCS in 2023, along with other green technologies, through its SDE++ subsidy. A new round was opened in June 2023 with a budget of EUR 8 billion that will allow, if fully allocated, to realise up to 4 Mtpa of CO₂ savings by 2030¹⁸⁴. The new envelope for this scheme was approved by the European Commission under EU State aid rules in July 2023. It provides a subsidy that could be applicable to CDR projects as well, such as BECCS and DACCS. Starting in 2035, no new CCS support will be granted.

¹⁸⁰ [European Commission. \(2023\). ETS Innovation Fund's closed-door knowledge sharing workshop: the emerging EU CO₂ transport and storage market.](#)

¹⁸¹ [NWO. \(2023\). Knowledge and Innovation Agendas \(KIAs\).](#)

¹⁸² [European Commission. \(2023\). Netherlands - Draft Updated NECP 2021-2030.](#)

¹⁸³ [Rijksdienst voor Ondernemend Nederland. \(2023\). Stimulering Duurzame Energieproductie en Klimaattransitie \(SDE++\).](#)

¹⁸⁴ [Egen Green. \(2023\). SDE++ grant round starts on 6 June – budget 8 billion.](#)

Demonstration Energy and Climate Innovation scheme (DEI+)¹⁸⁵: CCS/CCU projects are eligible only for pilot project funding. Temporary or permanent CO₂ storage on land is not eligible.

The **Environmental Investment Deduction (MIA)** and the **Random Depreciation of Environmental Investments (VAMIL)** are two schemes providing investment support for CCS/CCU projects¹⁸⁶.

The **Top Sector Energy Scheme (TSE)** provides subsidies for pilot and demonstration projects¹⁸⁷.

The **Energy Investment Deduction (IEA)** scheme provides tax deductions for CO₂ capture for permanent storage¹⁸⁸.

1.11.5 Projects

The **Porthos Project**¹⁸⁹ (domestic joint venture between the Port of Rotterdam Authority, Gasunie, and EBN) has taken the FID for the development of the first large-scale CO₂ transport and storage system. With construction set to start in 2024, Porthos is expected to be operational by 2026 and aims to store 2.5 Mtpa of CO₂ for 15 years (37 Mtpa of CO₂ in total).

The **Aramis Project**¹⁹⁰ (PCI, domestic joint venture between TotalEnergies, Shell, EBN, and Gasunie) will enable the transport of CO₂ to depleted offshore gas fields under the North Sea. It will aim to transport and store 22 Mtpa of CO₂ by 2030.

The **Neptune Energy Project**¹⁹¹ is pushing ahead with its L10 storage project that is expected to be able to store 120 to 150 Mtpa of CO₂ (supplied through the Aramis pipeline as well as by ships). The first CO₂ injection is expected in 2026.

The **Noordkaap Project**¹⁹² (cross-border joint venture between CapeOmega and Neptune Energy) will transport and store offshore biogenic CO₂ from a biomass plant along the North Sea coast using vessels suitable for directly injecting the CO₂ at offshore locations.

¹⁸⁵ [Rijksdienst voor Ondernemend Nederland. \(2023\). Demonstratie Energie- en Klimaatinnovatie \(DEI+\).](#)

¹⁸⁶ [Rijksdienst voor Ondernemend Nederland. \(2023\). MIA and VAMIL.](#)

¹⁸⁷ [Rijksdienst voor Ondernemend Nederland. \(2019\). Topsector Energie.](#)

¹⁸⁸ [Rijksdienst voor Ondernemend Nederland. \(2017\). Energie-investeringsaftrek \(EIA\) voor ondernemers.](#)

¹⁸⁹ [Porthos. \(n.d.\). CO₂ reduction through storage under the North Sea.](#)

¹⁹⁰ [Aramis. \(n.d.\). A large-scale CO₂ transport and storage service.](#)

¹⁹¹ [Neptune Energy. \(2023\). Dutch large scale CO₂ storage project L10CCS reaches FEED phase.](#)

¹⁹² [Neptune Energy. \(2023\). CapeOmega, Neptune announce cross-border CO₂ transport & storage development.](#)

The **CO2Transports Project**¹⁹³ (PCI, cross-border) aims to establish infrastructure to facilitate large-scale capture, transport, and storage of CO₂ from the ports of Rotterdam, Antwerp, and the North Sea through pipelines.

The **Delta Rhine Corridor Project**¹⁹⁴ (cross-border joint venture between BASF, Gasunie, OGE, and Shell) would connect Germany to the ports of Rotterdam and Antwerp through a network of CO₂ pipelines linking to the Aramis project for the storage part. It aims to be operational in 2028 and capacity of the pipeline will be between 4 to 10 Mtpa.

The **Air Products Project**¹⁹⁵ will build, own, and operate a carbon capture and CO₂ treatment facility at its existing hydrogen production plant in Rotterdam. The facility is expected to be operational in 2026 and will be the largest blue hydrogen plant in Europe.

The **RWE Project**¹⁹⁶ will launch a BECCUS project for large-scale capture and storage of CO₂ as well as a Taskforce Negative Emissions.

The **Vlissingen Cryocap FG Project**¹⁹⁷ (joint venture between Air Liquide, TotalEnergies, and Lukoil) will provide a carbon capture and liquefaction solution. It will have the capacity to liquefy 2,400 tonnes of CO₂ per day and capture more than 800,000 tonnes per year. The pure and liquefied carbon dioxide will then be transported for storage in the Dutch North Sea.

The **Carbon Connect Delta Project**¹⁹⁸ has the ambition to capture, transport, and store 6.5 Mt of CO₂ by 2030 in the Scheldt Delta region.

The **Yara Sluiskil Project**¹⁹⁹ (cross-border joint venture between Yara and Northern Lights) will reduce its annual CO₂ emissions by 800,000 tonnes by storing CO₂ deep under the Norwegian seabed from 2025.

The **AEB Amsterdam Project**²⁰⁰ is a waste management service providing waste-to-energy by processing residual waste from municipalities and businesses and extracting valuable materials before efficiently incinerating the remainder.

¹⁹³ [European Commission. \(2023\). CO2 TransPorts aims to establish infrastructure to facilitate large-scale capture, transport and storage of CO2 from Rotterdam, Antwerp and the North Sea Port.](#)

¹⁹⁴ [Delta Rhine Corridor. \(n.d.\). For more movement on energy and climate in Europe.](#)

¹⁹⁵ [Air Products. \(2023\). Air Products to Build Europe's Largest Blue Hydrogen Plant and Strengthens Long-term Agreement.](#)

¹⁹⁶ [RWE. \(2023\). RWE's BECCUS project to play crucial role in climate-neutral Dutch energy system through emission reduction and carbon removal.](#)

¹⁹⁷ [Air Liquide. \(2021\). Air Liquide Engineering & Construction supports decarbonization of Zeeland Refinery.](#)

¹⁹⁸ [Gasunie. \(n.d.\). Carbon Connect Delta.](#)

¹⁹⁹ [Yara. \(2023\). Yara invests in CCS in Sluiskil and signs binding CO2 transport and storage agreement with Northern Lights – the world's first cross-border CCS-agreement in operation.](#)

²⁰⁰ [AEB. \(n.d.\). What do we do?](#)

1.11.6 Bilateral agreements

The Netherlands and Belgium: signed an MoU on the cross-border transportation of CO₂ between the two countries with the purpose of permanent geological storage²⁰¹.

The Netherlands and Switzerland: signed a MoU to strengthen cooperation in the field of CCS/CCU²⁰².

The Netherlands and Denmark: signed a MoU to strengthen cooperation in the field of CCS/CCU²⁰³.

The Netherlands and Norway: signed a MoU to strengthen cooperation in the field of CCS²⁰⁴.

The Netherlands and France: signed a Pact for Innovation and Sustainable Growth (includes CCS/CCU)²⁰⁵.

1.12 Türkiye

1.12.1 Reduction and removal targets

Specific targets for emission reduction and removals have not been identified.

1.12.2 Legal framework

Türkiye is currently drafting a national climate law²⁰⁶.

1.12.3 Potential capacity

Specific data on the CO₂ storage capacity in Türkiye has not been identified.

²⁰¹ [Memorandum of understanding between the Minister for Environment of the Flemish Region and the Federal Minister for the North Sea of Belgium and the Minister for Energy and Climate of the Walloon Region and the Minister of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy of the Netherlands on cross border transportation of CO₂ with the purpose of permanent geological storage.](#)

²⁰² [Memorandum of understanding \(MoU\) between the State Secretary for Economic Affairs and Climate Policy of the Netherlands and the Head of the Federal Department of Environment, Transport, Energy and Communications of Switzerland on cooperation on carbon capture and storage \(CCS\) and carbon dioxide removal \(CDR\).](#)

²⁰³ [Memorandum of understanding \(MoU\) between the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy of the Netherlands and the Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities of Denmark on cooperation on carbon capture utilisation and storage \(CCUS\).](#)

²⁰⁴ [Memorandum of Understanding to promote bilateral cooperation in the field of carbon capture and storage \(CCS\), and exploring future areas of energy cooperation related to the North Sea.](#)

²⁰⁵ [Le Ministère de l'Économie et des Finances et de la Souveraineté Industrielle et Numérique. \(2023\). France and the Netherlands sign a pact for innovation and sustainable growth.](#)

²⁰⁶ [Altinay & Kohen. \(2024\). Climate Law on its way in Türkiye.](#)

1.12.4 Research, innovation, and funding

Boğaziçi University's İstanbul Microalgae Biotechnologies Research and Development Center (İMBİYOTAB) is involved in research related to CCU through the use of microalgae (see 1.12.6 projects).

No specific funding mechanisms for CCS and CCU have been identified.

1.12.5 Projects

Integrated Biorefinery Concept for Bio-economy Driven Development (INDEPENDENT) project: İMBİYOTAB, established in 2017 at the Sarıtepe Campus, is constructing Europe's first carbon-negative biorefinery focused on algae research²⁰⁷. The INDEPENDENT project is supported by the Competitive Sectors Programme and coordinated by the Ministry of Industry and Technology. İMBİYOTAB has also partnered with Turkish Airlines to produce algae biofuel²⁰⁸. The project will run until December 2027.

1.12.6 Bilateral agreements

No bilateral agreements have been identified.

1.13 United Kingdom

1.13.1 Reduction and removal targets

The Net Zero Strategy²⁰⁹ outlines the UK government's roadmap to net zero emissions. It aims to deploy a minimum of 5 Mt CO₂ annually through engineered removals by 2030, aligning with recommendations from the UK's independent Climate Change Committee (CCC) as per its 2021 progress report. The CCC foresees 58 Mt of engineered and 39 Mt of nature based GHG removals annually in the UK by 2050, following its Balanced Net Zero Pathway²¹⁰.

In August 2023, the government released its Biomass Strategy alongside a report assessing the viability of BECCS as a greenhouse gas removal (GGR) method. The report concluded that there were no insurmountable scientific barriers to GGR via BECCS provided appropriate sustainability criteria and sustainable supply chains are employed²¹¹.

²⁰⁷ [Boğaziçi University. \(2018\). Boğaziçi University will build Turkey and Europe's first carbon negative integrated biorefinery.](#)

²⁰⁸ [Bouscaren. \(2022\). This Turkish lab is turning algae into jet fuel.](#)

²⁰⁹ [Department for Energy Security and Net Zero & Department for Business and Energy and Industrial Strategy. \(2022\). Net Zero Strategy: Build Back Greener.](#)

²¹⁰ [Department for Energy Security and Net Zero et al. \(2023\). Developing the UK Emissions Trading Scheme \(UK ETS\).](#)

²¹¹ [Department for Energy Security and Net Zero. \(2023\). Biomass strategy.](#)

The UK's CCUS Vision²¹², launched in December 2023, outlines a comprehensive strategy for advancing CCS and CCU initiatives in the country. It sets targets for the sector's growth, aiming to achieve 20 to 30 Mtpa of CO₂ capture by 2030. Key components of the vision include fostering innovation and investment in CCUS technologies, establishing regulatory frameworks to support industry development, and facilitating the deployment of CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure. Additionally, the document highlights the importance of collaboration between government, industry, and research institutions to drive forward the UK's transition to a low-carbon economy while addressing climate change mitigation goals.

1.13.2 Legal framework

The Climate Change Act of 2008²¹³, with its amendment setting a 2050 target, legally binds the UK government to achieving net zero emissions by 2050. This legislation mandates the government to establish legally binding carbon budgets, which limit the amount of GHG emitted in the UK over successive five-year periods.

Additionally, the Energy Act establishes the regulatory framework and support mechanisms for CO₂ transport and storage networks, along with commercial arrangements for industrial CCS²¹⁴. According to the Act, the transportation of CO₂ via pipeline for geological storage operations necessitates a license and will be overseen by Ofgem, the economic regulator. Furthermore, the Act empowers the North Sea Transition Authority (NSTA) to gather data from companies holding carbon storage licenses, enhancing the understanding of the UK's carbon storage potential.

1.13.3 Potential capacity

According to the British Geological Survey, the UK has the potential to store over 70 Gt of CO₂ under the UK seabed²¹⁵.

1.13.4 Research, innovation, and funding

In 2020, the UK government, alongside its research arm UKRI, allocated GBP 100 million for research, development, and demonstration of GGR technologies through various programmes. This funding encompasses resources for establishing a central hub dedicated to carbon removal and initiating five land-based CDR demonstrator projects, including endeavours in enhanced weathering and biochar²¹⁶. Furthermore, it encompasses a competition focusing on DAC and other GGR technologies, aiming to

²¹² [Department for Energy Security and Net Zero. \(2023\). Carbon capture, usage and storage: a vision to establish a competitive market.](#)

²¹³ [Legislation.gov.uk. \(2024\). Climate Change Act 2008.](#)

²¹⁴ [Legislation.gov.uk. \(2023\). Energy Act 2023.](#)

²¹⁵ [British Geological Survey. \(n.d.\). CO₂ storage capacity estimation.](#)

²¹⁶ [CO₂RE.](#)

establish multiple operational pilot plants by 2025²¹⁷. Phase 1 of the GBP 60 million programme entailed conducting 22 feasibility studies across DAC, enhanced weathering, biochar, and BECCS technologies. Subsequently, in phase 2 of the competition, GBP 54.4 million in government funding was awarded to 15 selected demonstration projects in 2022.

Substantial funding commitments have also been made toward the advancement of the CCS/CCU and the development of CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure. The CCUS Vision²¹⁸ reaffirmed a GBP 20 billion funding allocation for CCS/CCU initiatives, delineating the UK's transition from a market creation phase in the 2020s (targeting 20 to 30 Mtpa by 2030) to a self-sustaining CCS/CCU market by 2035. In May 2023, the NSTA issued the first round of 20 carbon storage licenses for offshore sites²¹⁹. Additionally, in December 2023, the NSTA initiated a call for evidence to solicit feedback on a carbon storage levy as a prospective mechanism to finance its stewardship of carbon storage licenses, in alignment with the Treasury's user pays principle²²⁰.

1.13.5 Projects

Track 1 and Track 2 clusters play integral roles in advancing CCS technologies and infrastructure in the UK. Track 1 clusters focus on accelerating the development and deployment of CCS/CCU projects in industrial hubs with high CO₂ emissions, such as the Humber and Teesside regions. These clusters aim to integrate multiple emitters with CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure, fostering collaboration between industry and government to drive innovation and scale up CCS/CCU operations²²¹.

Track 2 clusters target areas with significant CO₂ storage potential, such as the North Sea, aiming to establish CO₂ transport and storage networks to support CCS projects²²². These clusters facilitate the development of regional CO₂ storage hubs and infrastructure, laying the foundation for widespread deployment of CCS technology across the UK.

²¹⁷ [Department for Energy Security and Net Zero & Department for Business and Energy and Industrial Strategy. \(2022\). Direct Air Capture and other Greenhouse Gas Removal technologies competition: selected projects.](#)

²¹⁸ [Department for Energy Security and Net Zero. \(2023\). Carbon capture, usage and storage: a vision to establish a competitive market.](#)

²¹⁹ [North Sea Transition Authority. \(2023\). Huge net zero boost as 20 carbon storage licences offered for award.](#)

²²⁰ [North Sea Transition Authority. \(2024\). Carbon Storage levy: Call for evidence response.](#)

²²¹ [Department for Energy Security and Net Zero. \(2023\). Carbon capture, usage and storage \(CCUS\) Track-1 cluster sequencing: evaluation.](#)

²²² [Department for Energy Security and Net Zero. \(2023\). Cluster sequencing for carbon capture, usage and storage \(CCUS\): Track-2.](#)

1.13.6 Bilateral agreements

UK and Denmark: MoU to cooperate on a path to net zero and long-term energy security (field of cooperation includes CCS/CCU)²²³.

UK and Norway: signed a MoU to strengthen cooperation in the field of CCS²²⁴.

UK and Spain: environmental MoU on Gibraltar, establishing the principle of cooperation for ensuring the highest standards of protection throughout the area, with the result that this will have an impact on such issues as solid and liquid waste management, the control of fuel supply to ships, and scientific research including marine research using specific ships for that purpose²²⁵.

²²³ [Department for Energy Security and Net Zero. \(2023\). Cooperation in the energy transition: UK - Denmark memorandum of understanding.](#)

²²⁴ [Memorandum of understanding between the Ministry of Petroleum and Energy of the Government of Norway and the Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy of the Government of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland on cooperation in the field of carbon capture usage and storage.](#)

²²⁵ [Memorando de entendimiento sobre cooperación en materia medioambiental.](#)

2 GOVERNMENT GROUP – PARTICIPATION OF NATIONAL GOVERNMENTS

The agendas for the Government Group meeting in June 2023 (Copenhagen, DK) and November 2023 (Berlin, DE) are included.

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 28 June 2023, 10.30 – 12.30 CEST

Hybrid meeting: Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities (Holmens Kanal 20 DK-1060 Copenhagen, Denmark) and Teams

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes – <i>pre-read 1</i> 	Jasmin Sharzad (Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities)	10:30 - 10:40
2 New ZEP Network Projects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up Possible coordination with Government Group 	ZEP Secretariat, All	10:40 – 10:55
3 Updates on national CCS/CCU developments Roundtable – Government Group member updates <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National developments: policy and funding Bilateral agreements National Energy and Climate Plans, ahead of the EU Strategy for CCS and CCU 	All	10:55 – 11:40
4 The Net-Zero Industry Act proposal <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP position – <i>pre-read 2</i> Other points to consider? 	ZEP Secretariat, All	11:40 – 11:55
5 Paris Agreement: carbon removals Article 6.4 mechanism <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP responses – <i>pre-reads 3, 4 and 5</i> Future actions? 	ZEP Secretariat, All	11:55 – 12:10
6 CCS updates from the Bonn Climate Change Conference	Stig Svenningsen (Norwegian Ministry of Petroleum and Energy)	12:10 – 12:25
7 Next meeting dates and AOB <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 20 September 2023 (10:30-15:00) – to be rescheduled 14 November 2023 (10:30-15:00, Berlin) 	ZEP Secretariat	12:25 – 12:30

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 14 November 2023, 10:00 – 12:00 CEST

Hybrid meeting: Scharnhorststraße 34-37, 10115 Berlin & Microsoft Teams

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes of the last meeting – <i>pre-read 1</i> 	Ministry for economic affairs and climate action of Germany (BMWK)	10:00 – 10:10
2 Germany's upcoming strategy on CCS and CCU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation 	Ministry for economic affairs and climate action of Germany (BMWK)	10:10 – 10:30
3 Updates on national CCS and CCU developments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roundtable – country updates 	All	10:30 – 11:00
4 Updates from ZEP <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Projects Network – presentation and coordination with the Government Group 	Stijn Santen, EBN (tbc)	11:00 – 11:10
5 Net Zero Industry Act and Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legislative state-of-play – <i>pre-read 2</i> Group discussion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> what are your views on the ENVI report? can the texts be finalised before the 2024 European Parliament election? 	ZEP secretariat, All	11:10 – 11:25
6 European Commission report on the implementation of the CO2 storage directive <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Main messages Implication regarding the London Protocol 	DG CLIMA (tbc)	11:25 – 11:35
7 European ports in cross-border CO2 transport (tbc) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> UK study 'CCUS Ports – Infrastructure Requirement Assessment' 	UK Department for Energy Security and Net Zero	11:35 – 11:55

8 Next meeting dates and AOB <ul style="list-style-type: none">• 2024 meeting dates	ZEP secretariat	11:55 – 12:00
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